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Services

Deliverable 4.3

FINAL RESULTS OF THE AI-DRIVEN ANOMALY DETECTION, DECISION & MITIGATION

Title	Final Results of the AI-Driven Anomaly Detection, Decision and Mitigation
Document description	This deliverable will report the final scientific outcomes from the four tasks as well as the final version of the implemented components and enablers.
Nature	Public

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Version 01	EBOS	23/05/2025	First round of inputs on AI-driven anomaly detection and mostly on EBOS assets
Version 02	OULU, UWS, WINGS	13/06/2025	Major contributions from partners related to their final version of the components in terms of architecture, data services, final results and updates related to the first prototype
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Final Version	WINGS	24/06/2025	Final formatting, complete list of acronyms, figures tables, etc. Modifications to adhere to the project templates. This version will be sent for peer review.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Explanation/ Definition
5G	Fifth Generation
6G	Sixth Generation
AE	AutoEncoder
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIAI	Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations
AID	AI-driven Decision Making/Engine
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
API	Application Programming Interface
B5G	Beyond 5th Generation (Networks)
BFL	Buffered Federated Learning
BS	Base Station
CICIDS2017/2018	Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity Intrusion Detection System 2017/2018 dataset
CNF	Cloud-Native Network Function
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CPC	Cyber Physical Correlator
CPRI	Common Public Radio Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSC	Customer Service Centre
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CTI	Cyber Threat Intelligence
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
CVSS	Common Vulnerability Scoring System
DASC	Dynamic and Automated Service Composition
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DL	Deep Learning
DM	Data Monitoring

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Dissemination level: PU

DoS	Denial of Service
DP	Differential Privacy
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DS	Data Services
DSP	Digital Service Providers
DT	Digital Twin
DU	Distributed Unit
Dx.y	Deliverable x.y
E1	Endpoint 1
E2	Endpoint 2
E2E	End-to-End
EaaS	Encryption as a Service
EDoS	Economic Denial of Sustainability
FDI	False Data Injection
FIN	Field Information Notice
FL	Federated Learning
FN	Federated Node
FNWF	Future Networks World Forum
FTC	Future Technologies Conference
GC	Global Coordinator
GENEVE	Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation
GRE	Generic Routing Encapsulation
GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
GTP	GPRS Tunnelling Protocol
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
HPA	Horizontal Pod Autoscaling
HSPF	Holistic Security and Privacy Framework
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HW	Hardware

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Dissemination level: PU

IAT	Intelligent Agent Technology
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ID	Identification
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
INIT	Initiation
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
IT	Information Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
K8s	Kubernetes
Kafka	Apache Kafka event streaming platform
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LTE	Long-Term Evolution
LTS	Long-Term Support
MAC	Media Access Control
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MIRO	Multi-domain Intelligence Resource Orchestration
MISP	Malware Information Sharing Platform
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSPL	Medium Security Policy Language
MTD	Moving Target Defence
MTD-FL	Moving Target Defense-based Federated Learning
MTU	Maximum Transmission Unit
NFStream	A Python Network Data Analysis Framework
NGAP	Next Generation Application Protocol

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NGINX	A Web and Proxy Server
NIDS	Network Intrusion Detection System
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NMap	Network Scanner/Mapper Tool
NSFM	Network Security Flow Monitoring
NSP	Network Service Provider
NVD	National Vulnerability Database
Open5GS	Open-source implementation of 5G Core Network Functions
OVS	OpenvSwitch
PCAP	Packet Capture
PET	Privacy Enhancing Technology
POST	Power-On-Self-Test
PPFL	Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning
PSH	Push
PV	Photovoltaic
RabbitMQ	A Message Broker
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
RES	Renewable Energy Source
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
RM	Response Mitigation
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
RSA	Rivest-Shamir-Adleman
RST	Reset
SA	Standalone (5G Core Network)
SACK	Selective Acknowledgements
SAE	Security Analytics Engine
SCTP	Stream Control Transmission Protocol
SMPS	Slicing Mitigation Planner Service

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SNORT	Open-source network intrusion detection and prevention system (IDS/IPS)
SO	Security Orchestrator
SOAR	Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSH	Secure Shell
STIX	Structured Threat Information eXpression
STIXv2	Structured Threat Information eXpression version 2
SW	Software
SYN	Synchronisation (flag)
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TIA	Topology Inventory Agent
TIP	Threat Intelligence Platform
TRA	Threat Risk Assessor
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UE	User Equipment
UERAN-SIM	Open-source state-of-the-art 5G UE and RAN (gNodeB) simulator
UI	User Interface
UPF	User Plane Function
URG	Urgent (flag)
vCDN	virtual Content Delivery Network
VXLAN	Virtual Extensible LAN
WP	Work Package
WUSTL-IIoT	Washington University in St. Louis IIoT dataset
XML	Extensible Markup Language
ZKP	Zero Knowledge Proof
ZTM	Zero Trust Model

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D4.3 outlines the final updates to the WP4 components, with emphasis on:

- Modular integration of AI-driven tools for anomaly detection, mitigation, and threat analysis.
- Advanced Federated Learning (FL) models for anomaly detection validated in multi-tenant 5G/6G environments.
- The deployment and validation of CPC (Cyber-Physical Correlator), DASC (Dynamic Automated Service Composition), SOAR (Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response), and the Digital Twin simulation framework in 5G testbeds.
- Use of privacy-preserving methods such as encryption-as-a-service, secure threat sharing, and policy enforcement.
- Seamless end-to-end security response loop from detection to mitigation.
- Contribution to network slicing defence, interoperability resolution, and real-time risk assessment.

Building on earlier deliverables (D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [2]), this document describes the evolution of all WP4 assets—from detection engines based on federated deep learning, to cognitive decision-making components that assess threat severity, to orchestration mechanisms that enforce dynamic and automated responses. These components form an intelligent end-to-end response framework, further enhanced by privacy-preserving techniques such as secure threat intelligence sharing, encryption-as-a-service, and moving target defence.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1. Scope

Deliverable D4.3 outlines the final technical results of WP4 of the RIGOUROUS project, focusing on AI-driven anomaly detection, decision-making, and automated mitigation components. It documents the finalized architectures, implementation updates, and integration status of all WP4 assets, including anomaly detection models, cognitive risk assessment engines, dynamic service composition mechanisms, security orchestration tools, and privacy-preserving AI modules.

D4.3 is considered an update of D4.2 [2] which provided the initial outcomes regarding WP4 assets, in terms of state-of-the-art analysis, RIGOUROUS advancements and asset descriptions. This deliverable presents the progress regarding the WP4 assets as of M30 (June 2025) in terms of component architecture, data services for the assets to function, attacks targeted and final results as well as updates related to the first prototype.

2.2. Objectives

The present deliverable adheres to WP4 objectives which focus on designing and developing anomaly detection, decision-making, and mitigation mechanisms using AI. Specifically, the WP aims to:

- Develop innovative AI-powered mechanisms for federated cross-domain analytics to detect anomalies with privacy protection and resilience to adversarial attacks.
- Create dynamic and automated service composition mechanisms that combine AI with rules-based systems to identify and resolve interconnection issues (interoperability, security, privacy, and trust mismatches) among components that need to interoperate but are not pre-defined.
- Build AI-driven modules for automated decision-making to determine appropriate mitigation strategies on a case-by-case basis.
- Establish enablers for a fully functional closed control loop for automated security mitigation against cyber-attacks.

2.3. Structure of the document

The document is organised as follows, where the corresponding assets are analysed in terms of architecture, data monitoring and data services, attacks targeted, final results, and updates related to the first prototype:

1. AI-Driven Anomaly Detection
 - a. Privacy-Preserving FL-Based Anomaly Detector
 - b. Privacy-Preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection
 - c. Holistic Security and Privacy Framework
 - d. AI-Driven Cyber-Physical Correlator
2. AI-Driven Cognitive Decision Making
 - a. AI-Driven Decision Making - AID
 - b. Threat Risk Assessor - TRA

3. AI-Driven Security Response-Mitigation
 - a. AI Powered EDoS Mitigator
 - b. Security Testing ? Digital Twin ? DT
 - c. Dynamic and Automated Service Composition ? DASC
 - d. AI-Driven 6G Response Mitigation
 - e. Slicing Mitigation Planner Service
4. SOAR Driven Network Flow and Topology Monitoring
 - a. Network Security Flow Monitoring
 - b. Topology Inventory Agent
5. Robust and Privacy Preserving AI
 - a. MTD based Robust AI
 - b. Encryption-as-a-Service
 - c. Privacy Preserving CTI Sharing

Also, there is a section dedicated to system interoperability and how the assets interoperate and act as one thing.

The document is complemented by corresponding lists of references, abbreviations, figures and tables.

3 AI-DRIVEN ANOMALY DETECTION

3.1. Introduction

The RIGOUROUS project is developing a suite of advanced, privacy-preserving anomaly detection solutions based on FL paradigm, with the goal of advancing the state-of-the-art in Beyond 5G (B5G) networks. These contributions (i) introduce novel learning models that leverage diverse Deep Learning (DL) algorithms that have been trained on both publicly available and custom-built datasets, (ii) enhance FL aggregation strategies, and (iii) strengthen privacy guarantees within the FL framework by adopting various Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs).

In D4.2 [2], we presented the preliminary implementation of these assets along with the initial results. This section reports the final outcomes, providing detailed insights into the component architecture and the supported data models, with a clear emphasis on the updates and enhancements made since the initial version documented in D4.2 [2]. The section concludes with a summary table outlining the key contributions and advancements achieved.

3.2. Privacy-Preserving FL-Based Anomaly Detector

3.2.1. Component Architecture

The "Privacy-Preserving FL-Based Anomaly Detector" aims to design an enhanced privacy-preserving, and communication-efficient anomaly detection framework tailored for Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) systems, capable of handling data heterogeneity, protecting sensitive information against cyber threats, and ensuring fast and accurate threat detection across heterogeneous industrial environments. To meet this challenge, two core modules have been developed:

1. A Privacy-Preserving Anomaly Detection Module based on FL enhanced with Homomorphic Encryption (HE).
2. A Buffered Aggregation Mechanism to mitigate straggler effects and communication bottlenecks.

The anomaly detection module empowers IIoT clients to collaboratively train a global deep learning model without sharing raw data. Using partial HE, model updates are encrypted during transit and aggregation, ensuring confidentiality throughout the training process. Moreover, the proposed Buffered Federated Learning (BFL) strategy [3] synchronizes model updates only from clients meeting a fairness-based training time threshold, thereby improving convergence speed and model accuracy in heterogeneous client settings. Further information is available in [4].

Figure 1 Interaction Flow Between Anomaly Detection FL (OULU) and EaaS (ICTF)

The system integrates a federated anomaly detection pipeline with **Encryption as a Service (EaaS)** and real-time alert dissemination via **Structured Threat Information eXpression (STIX) messages**. As illustrated in Figure 1, the process is executed in two primary loops: one for local training and encryption, and another for global aggregation and secure communication between IIoT clients and the EaaS server.

Each training iteration begins with local model updates by clients (IoT agents), which are then encrypted via EaaS. The encrypted model weights are aggregated by the central server and subsequently decrypted again by EaaS for use in further local updates. This separation of learning and encryption enhances modularity, privacy, and trust.

Figure 2 Federated anomaly detection workflow with encrypted model exchange

Meanwhile, as shown in Figure 2, after the anomaly detector processes new network flows, it generates **STIX-compliant messages** containing:

- The model information (e.g., model ID, architecture, training framework).
- Anomaly detection results (e.g., confidence score, anomaly label, IPs and ports).
- A semantic relationship (relationship_type: "indicates") linking the model to the anomaly.

These STIX bundles are then published to the **Decision Engine** via a Kafka bus for real-time threat handling and policy execution.

3.2.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

Generated STIX response message and request formats are shown in the following (see Table 1 and Table 2), for both the schema and an example of actual parameters.

Table 1 Input Parameters and Output Schema of the API

Field	Description
Request Schema	The number of iterations: int The number of local epochs: int Type of classification: string
Request Example	The number of iterations: 10 The number of local epochs: 10 Type of classification: binary

Table 2 Data Model, in STIX format, of Anomaly Report Generated by Privacy-Preserving FL-based Detector

Field	Description
Response Schema	<pre> { "type": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "testbed": "STRING", "objects": [{ "type": "anomaly", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "STRING", "created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "value": "FLOAT", "value_type": "STRING", "flow_id": "STRING", "source_ip": "STRING", "source_port": "INTEGER", "destination_ip": "STRING", "destination_port": "INTEGER", "flow_data": "ARRAY of FLOAT", "label": "STRING", "anomaly_name": "STRING" }, { "type": "model", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "STRING", "created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "model_id": "STRING", "model_name": "STRING", "learning_type": "STRING", "flow_features": "ARRAY of STRING", "multi_class_accuracy": "FLOAT", "comparison_metric": "STRING", "framework": "STRING", "framework_version": "STRING", "collection_tool": "STRING", "collection_tool_version": "STRING", "training_timestamp": "INTEGER" }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "STRING", </pre>

	<pre>"created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "relationship_type": "STRING", "source_ref": "STRING", "target_ref": "STRING" }] }</pre>
Response Example	<pre>{ "type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--80dc1e62-373a-43b8-86e9-5969d0444982", "testbed": "oulu", "objects": [{ "type": "model", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "model--a26d1ec0-e90d-41b8-ae03-a00de8e9e31d", "created": "2025-05-09T09:55:37.902935Z", "modified": "2025-05-09T09:55:37.902935Z", "model_id": "client0_model", "model_name": "MLP", "learning_type": "mult", "flow_features": ["Init_Win_bytes_forward", "SYN_Flag_Count", "Bwd_Packet_Length_Mean", "Flow_Packets_Sec", ... "Label", "muntiLabel", "binLabel"], "multi_class_accuracy": 99.43670548831544, "comparison_metric": "softmax", "framework": "PyTorch", "framework_version": "2.3.0+cu121", "collection_tool": "", "collection_tool_version": "", "training_timestamp": 1746784537 }, { "type": "anomaly", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomaly--380b017a-f650-4974-840e-21c5113d9345", "created": "2025-05-09T09:55:46.98559Z", "modified": "2025-05-09T09:55:46.98559Z", }] }</pre>

	<pre>"flow_id": "0", "value": 0.19190973043441772, "value_type": "confidence", "anomaly_name": "GoldenEye", "source_ip": "192.168.1.171", "source_port": 8001, "destination_ip": "192.168.1.19", "destination_port": 8803, "flow_data": [0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 4.253026730793863e-08, ... 0.008414766751229763, 0.0], "label": "goldeneye" }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--c7d805d2-11d5-4bfc-a9c9-ee0c79a4c4b1", "created": "2025-05-09T09:55:47.162235Z", "modified": "2025-05-09T09:55:47.162235Z", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "model--a26d1ec0-e90d-41b8-ae03-a00de8e9e31d", "target_ref": "anomaly--380b017a-f650-4974-840e-21c5113d9345" }]</pre>
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3.2.3. Attacks targeted

The evaluation focuses on detecting several prominent Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks based on the labelled samples from the DDoS-Sandbox¹ dataset. The DDoS-Sandbox dataset consists of flow-level network traffic records generated in a controlled testbed environment. The dataset is created by combining:

- Our previous dataset [4] generated in the frame of INSPIRE-5Gplus project. This dataset contains Benign, Slowloris, and Hulk traffic.
- Benign and High-rate HTTP DDoS traffic (generated using GoldenEye tool) extracted from CICIDS-2018 dataset [37].

- High and low-rate HTTP DDoS attack traffic generated in OULU's 5G testbed (see Section 3.3.3.2 in Deliverable D5.2 [5] for more details on this testbed) using GoldenEye [6], Hulken [7], and Slowloris [8] tools.

Each record includes statistical and behavioural features that describe the characteristics of a network flow. These features capture various aspects of traffic, such as packet sizes, flow durations, inter-arrival times, TCP flag occurrences, and window sizes. It contains both benign and malicious traffic samples, particularly targeting several types of DoS attacks. The distribution of targeted attacks is as follows:

- DoS Hulk
- DoS Slowloris
- DoS GoldenEye
- Slowloris
- Hulken

3.2.4. Final Results

The final prototype was deployed using two clients and one aggregator server within a FL setup. It was implemented through a Flask-based RESTful API to simulate client-server communication in a controlled environment. As demonstrated in Table 1, the system achieved a multi-class classification accuracy of 99.43% using an MLP (Multi-Layer Perceptron) model trained with PyTorch. It successfully detected a GoldenEye DoS attack. All results were structured in STIX format, including model metadata and the relationship between the model and the detected anomaly.

3.2.5. Updates related to the first prototype

In the initial prototype, our work was based on a public dataset, WUSTL-IIoT, and focused on generating two basic STIX messages. In the updated version, we extended the scenario to include two IIoT clients and one aggregator server. The new setup can receive structured requests and generate more comprehensive and well-structured STIX messages using a real-world sandbox dataset.

3.3. Privacy-Preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection

3.3.1. Component Architecture

Figure 3 Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection asset architecture and integration

The asset architecture, shown in Figure 3, has been extended from the version presented in Deliverable D4.2 [2]. It is composed of a Monitoring & Analytics block which contains the main AI logic, and a 6G Infrastructure Layer where the distributed training process occurs. The core logic is located within the Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection (UMU) component, which generates its outputs through two endpoints (E1, E2) using the STIXv2 format.

The training process leverages an FL framework within the 6G Infrastructure Layer, composed of multiple FL Agents and a central FL Aggregator. To enhance privacy and security, the FL process has been updated with new mechanisms. In addition to existing methods, the aggregator now supports model clipping to limit the impact of individual model updates. The range of noise-adding functions for Differential Privacy (DP) has also been expanded to include Gaussian, Laplacian, Uniform, Exponential, and Salt & Pepper noise, creating a more robust training framework against potential attacks.

The Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection asset contains two main engines:

1. **Anomaly Detection Engine:** This engine uses a Deep Autoencoder to identify anomalous traffic. The model is trained using the aforementioned FL process. Its implementation has been optimized to reduce prediction times.
2. **Attack Classification Engine:** This engine employs a Deep Neural Network for multi-class classification to assign a specific attack label to any flow flagged as an anomaly. It is trained in a centralized way from a static dataset. This model has also been optimized for faster performance.

The collaboration between the models is managed through an internal REST API. When the Anomaly Detection Engine identifies an anomalous flow, it sends a request to the Attack Classification Engine to get the corresponding attack label. The final output combines this information.

Several enhancements have been integrated into the overall system. A new model has been included to specifically provide detection and classification of control plane attacks, extending the system's scope beyond traditional user plane threats. The datasets used for training and testing both attack types are generated using UMU's proprietary monitoring sensors and flow processors,

which produce unique and extensible flow features. Furthermore, the preprocessing techniques and detection models have been optimized to increase performance metrics such as accuracy and recall on the considered set of attacks.

The asset provides its information through the following STIXv2-formatted endpoints:

- **E1 Detection models information:** Through a REST API, this endpoint offers information about the models used for both anomaly detection and attack classification. For the Deep Autoencoder and the Deep Neural Network, details such as the flow features used for training, the obtained accuracy, and Machine Learning (ML) framework information are available. This now includes details for the models covering control plane attacks.
- **E2 Real-time anomaly alerts:** Through a Kafka broker, the asset publishes information for each flow detected as anomalous in real-time. This information includes flow identifiers (IPs, ports), the attack label assigned by the Attack Classification Engine, the reconstruction error for the anomaly detection, and the confidence level for the attack classification. A reference to the specific models used is also included, allowing the information from E2 to be mapped to the model details provided by E1.

3.3.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

For this final version of the asset, UMU's proprietary monitoring and flow processing solutions have been leveraged. These solutions replace the previous approach of using public datasets and provide a complete pipeline for both dataset generation and real-time analysis, fulfilling the roles of the Data Monitoring (DM) and Data Services (DS) functional blocks.

The architecture of this solution is based on an in-house developed real-time packet monitoring and flow processing software deployed in the UMU testbed. The process is as follows:

- A **monitoring module** captures traffic from a designated network interface, creating real-time packet summaries that contain relevant fields from different protocol layers (e.g., IP addresses, TTL values, TCP flags).
- These packet summaries are published to a Kafka topic.
- A **flow processor module** consumes the summaries from Kafka, aggregates the packet information into flow-based statistics, and calculates a set of features.
- These resulting flow statistics are then published to another Kafka topic. This final topic serves as the data source for the consumers: for the FL agents during the training phase, and for the Anomaly Detection Engine for real-time evaluation.

This pipeline is used for two primary functions: first, to generate static datasets (in CSV format) by capturing and processing traffic from simulated benign and malicious scenarios; and second, to feed the detection engines with a live stream of flow data for real-time prediction. Using this methodology, two distinct datasets have been generated to train and evaluate the asset: one for user plane attacks and one for control plane attacks.

The user plane dataset is characterized by a comprehensive set of 83 features, calculated for each flow. These features cover general flow statistics as well as protocol-specific metrics for ICMP, UDP, and TCP. The complete list of features is detailed in Table 3.

Table 3 List of user plane traffic flow features used for detection

Feature Number	Feature Name	Feature Description
F1	ul_ip	Uplink/source IP
F2	dl_ip	Downlink/destination IP
F3	ul_port	Uplink/source port
F4	dl_port	Downlink/destination port

F5	duration	Duration in microseconds
F6	numpacket_s_ul	Number of packets sent in Uplink
F7	numpacket_s_dl	Number of packets sent in Downlink
F8	numpacket_s_ratio	Ratio between Uplink and Downlink packets
F9	numpacket_s_1s_ul	Number of packets sent in one second in Uplink
F10	numpacket_s_1s_dl	Number of packets sent in one second in Downlink
F11	numbytes_ul	Number of bytes sent in Uplink
F12	numbytes_dl	Number of bytes sent in Downlink
F13	bits_1s_ul	Average bits per second in Uplink
F14	bits_1s_dl	Average bits per second in Downlink
F15	max_packet_size_ul	Maximal packet size in Uplink
F16	max_packet_size_dl	Maximal packet size in Downlink
F17	min_packet_size_ul	Minimal packet size in Uplink
F18	min_packet_size_dl	Minimal packet size in Downlink
F19	avg_packet_size_ul	Average packet size in Uplink
F20	avg_packet_size_dl	Average packet size in Downlink
F21	stddev_packetsize_ul	Variability of size between packets in Uplink
F22	stddev_packetsize_dl	Variability of size between packets in Downlink
F23	max_ttl_ul	Maximal time-to-live (TTL) in Uplink
F24	max_ttl_dl	Maximal time-to-live (TTL) in Downlink
F25	min_ttl_ul	Minimal time-to-live (TTL) in Uplink
F26	min_ttl_dl	Minimal time-to-live (TTL) in Downlink
F27	avg_ttl_ul	Average time-to-live (TTL) in Uplink
F28	avg_ttl_dl	Average time-to-live (TTL) in Downlink
F29	stddev_ttl_ul	Variability of TTL between packets in Uplink
F30	stddev_ttl_dl	Variability of TTL between packets in Downlink
F31	max_iat_ul	Max time between consecutive packets (IAT) in Uplink
F32	max_iat_dl	Max time between consecutive packets (IAT) in Downlink

F33	min_iat_ul	Min time between consecutive packets (IAT) in Uplink
F34	min_iat_dl	Min time between consecutive packets (IAT) in Downlink
F35	avg_iat_ul	Average time between consecutive packets (IAT) in Uplink
F36	avg_iat_dl	Average time between consecutive packets (IAT) in Downlink
F37	stddev_iat_ul	Variability of IAT between packets in Uplink
F38	stddev_iat_dl	Variability of IAT between packets in Downlink
F39	icmp_duration	ICMP session duration in microseconds
F40	icmp_num_packets_ul	Number of ICMP packets sent in Uplink
F41	icmp_num_packets_dl	Number of ICMP packets sent in Downlink
F42	icmp_bits_1s_ul	Average ICMP bits per second in Uplink
F43	icmp_bits_1s_dl	Average ICMP bits per second in Downlink
F44	udp_duration	UDP session duration in microseconds
F45	udp_num_packets_ul	Number of UDP packets sent in Uplink
F46	udp_num_packets_dl	Number of UDP packets sent in Downlink
F47	udp_bits_1s_ul	Average UDP bits per second in Uplink
F48	udp_bits_1s_dl	Average UDP bits per second in Downlink
F49	udp_max_packet_size_ul	UDP Maximal packet size in Uplink
F50	udp_max_packet_size_dl	UDP Maximal packet size in Downlink
F51	udp_min_packet_size_ul	UDP Minimal packet size in Uplink
F52	udp_min_packet_size_dl	UDP Minimal packet size in Downlink
F53	udp_avg_packet_size_ul	UDP Average packet size in Uplink
F54	udp_avg_packet_size_dl	UDP Average packet size in Downlink

F55	tcp_duration	TCP session duration in microseconds
F56	tcp_num_packets_ul	Number of TCP packets in Uplink
F57	tcp_num_packets_dl	Number of TCP packets in Downlink
F58	tcp_bits_1s_ul	Avg. TCP bits per second in Uplink
F59	tcp_bits_1s_dl	Avg. TCP bits per second in Downlink
F60	tcp_max_packet_size_ul	TCP Maximal packet size in Uplink
F61	tcp_max_packet_size_dl	TCP Maximal packet size in Downlink
F62	tcp_min_packet_size_ul	TCP Minimal packet size in Uplink
F63	tcp_min_packet_size_dl	TCP Minimal packet size in Downlink
F64	tcp_avg_packet_size_ul	TCP Average packet size in Uplink
F65	tcp_avg_packet_size_dl	TCP Average packet size in Downlink
F66	tcp_max_window_size_ul	TCP Maximal window size in Uplink
F67	tcp_max_window_size_dl	TCP Maximal window size in Downlink
F68	tcp_min_window_size_ul	TCP Minimal window size in Uplink
F69	tcp_min_window_size_dl	TCP Minimal window size in Downlink
F70	tcp_avg_window_size_ul	TCP Average window size in Uplink
F71	tcp_avg_window_size_dl	TCP Average window size in Downlink
F72	tcp_num_packets_fin_ul	Number of TCP packets with FIN flag set in Uplink
F73	tcp_num_packets_fin_dl	Number of TCP packets with FIN flag set in Downlink
F74	tcp_num_packets_syn_ul	Number of TCP packets with SYN flag set in Uplink

	ckets_syn_ul	
F75	tcp_numpackets_syn_dl	Number of TCP packets with SYN flag set in Downlink
F76	tcp_numpackets_rst_ul	Number of TCP packets with RST flag set in Uplink
F77	tcp_numpackets_rst_dl	Number of TCP packets with RST flag set in Downlink
F78	tcp_numpackets_psh_ul	Number of TCP packets with PSH flag set in Uplink
F79	tcp_numpackets_psh_dl	Number of TCP packets with PSH flag set in Downlink
F80	tcp_numpackets_ack_ul	Number of TCP packets with ACK flag set in Uplink
F81	tcp_numpackets_ack_dl	Number of TCP packets with ACK flag set in Downlink
F82	tcp_numpackets_urg_ul	Number of TCP packets with URG flag set in Uplink
F83	tcp_numpackets_urg_dl	Number of TCP packets with URG flag set in Downlink

For the detection of control plane attacks, a specialized dataset was created. Its features focus on the specifics of control plane protocols in 5G networks, primarily NGAP (Next Generation Application Protocol) and its transport protocol SCTP (Stream Control Transmission Protocol). These features count the occurrences of specific message types, procedure codes, and protocol flags within a flow. The full list is provided in Table 4.

Table 4 List of control plane traffic flow features used for detection

Feature Number	Feature Name	Feature Description
F1	ul_ip	Uplink/source IP
F2	dl_ip	Downlink/destination IP
F3	ul_port	Uplink/source port
F4	dl_port	Downlink/destination port
F5	flow_durati	Total duration of the flow in microseconds

F6	flow_id	A unique identifier for the flow
F7	ngap_crit_0_count	Count of NGAP messages with criticality 'reject'
F8	ngap_crit_1_count	Count of NGAP messages with criticality 'ignore'
F9	ngap_crit_ignore_count	Count of NGAP messages with criticality 'ignore'
F10	ngap_crit_notify_count	Count of NGAP messages with criticality 'notify'
F11	ngap_crit_reject_count	Count of NGAP messages with criticality 'reject'
F12	ngap_msgtype_0_count	Count of NGAP messages of type 'initiatingMessage'
F13	ngap_msgtype_32_count	Count of NGAP messages with a specific type ID
F14	ngap_msgtype_initiating_message_count	Count of NGAP messages of type 'initiatingMessage'
F15	ngap_msgtype_successfuloutcome_count	Count of NGAP messages of type 'successfulOutcome'
F16	ngap_msgtype_unsuccessfuloutcome_count	Count of NGAP messages of type 'unsuccessfulOutcome'
F17 - F68	ngap_proc_1_count ... ngap_proc_52_count	Count of messages for each specific NGAP Procedure Code
F69	packet_size_max	Maximum packet size observed in the flow
F70	packet_size_mean	Average packet size of the flow
F71	packet_size_min	Minimum packet size observed in the flow
F72	packet_size_stddev	Standard deviation of packet sizes in the flow
F73 - F88	sctp_chunk_0_count ... sctp_chunk_15_count	Count of chunks for each specific SCTP Chunk Type (e.g., DATA, INIT, SACK)

	15_count	
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3.3.3. Attacks targeted

The list of attacks considered is detailed below:

- **User plane:** TCP SYN DoS (with *hping3* tool) and brute-force dictionary-based attacks (with open-source scripts). Specifically, HTTP and SSH protocols have been used to perform the brute force attack (generating the attacks named HTTP Dict and SSH Dict).
- **Control plane:** AMF Registration Requests DoS. For this attack type, the traffic generated in UMU 5G testbed during the experiments run by LNVO was processed and used to construct the malign profile. For the benign profile, traffic generated from several days of normal activities in the testbed has been leveraged.

The traffic relative to all attacks targeted (and thereby the datasets) has been generated, monitored and processed in UMU 5G testbed.

3.3.4. Final Results

This section presents the final performance results of the asset, evaluating the effectiveness of the detection models under different DP configurations. The evaluation was conducted using the two distinct datasets generated with the proprietary monitoring solution: the user plane attack dataset and the control plane attack dataset (each one with benign traffic samples and samples for each attack described in Section 3.3.3). The key metrics of Accuracy, Recall, and F1 Score were calculated for the baseline scenario without DP ("No DP") and for each of the five newly integrated noise-adding mechanisms.

The experiments have been executed in an FL scenario composed of 2 clients. A total of 10 learning rounds, with 5 local epochs per round are run. Each mechanism has been configured with a noise standard deviation of 0.25, considered the optimal trade-off between accuracy and privacy obtained. In addition, model updates clipping (with norm = 1) has been applied. For the user plane attacks detection, the Anomaly Detection Engine model (Deep Autoencoder) has been tested, while for the control plane datasets, a supervised MLP is considered.

The results for the user plane attack dataset are illustrated in Figure 4. The model demonstrates a high level of performance across all scenarios. In the baseline "No-DP" configuration, the asset achieves an F1 Score of approximately 0.951, with an exceptionally high Recall of 0.9985. When DP mechanisms are introduced, the impact on performance varies. The application of Gaussian and Laplacian noise results in a slight, manageable reduction in performance, with F1 Scores around 0.92. Notably, the Uniform, Exponential, and Salt and Pepper noise mechanisms show a negligible impact on model utility. These configurations maintain F1 Scores above 0.948 and preserve the near-perfect Recall of 0.9985, demonstrating that privacy can be enforced with minimal sacrifice to the detection capability for user plane attacks.

An interesting observation is that the Salt and Pepper and Exponential mechanisms slightly outperform the no-DP baseline. This phenomenon can occur when the addition of noise to the model updates acts as a form of regularization. By preventing the model from overfitting to the specific characteristics of the training data, the noise can improve its ability to generalize to new, unseen data, leading to a marginal increase in performance on the test set.

Figure 4 Performance metrics for each noise-adding mechanisms considering the user plane attack dataset

Figure 5 Performance metrics for each noise-adding mechanisms considering the control plane attack dataset

The performance of the asset on the control plane attack dataset is shown in Figure 5. The model achieves near-perfect results in the "No DP" baseline scenario, with all three metrics at 0.9996. The impact of the noise-adding mechanisms is significantly more pronounced and varied in this use case. Gaussian and Uniform noise prove to be highly effective, maintaining excellent performance with F1 Scores of 0.9916 and 0.9943, respectively. Exponential noise also performs strongly, achieving an F1 Score of 0.9783. In contrast, Laplacian noise causes a substantial drop in performance, with the F1 Score decreasing to approximately 0.775. The Salt and Pepper mechanism is shown to be unsuitable for this specific model and data distribution, as it leads to a severe degradation in performance, with the F1 Score falling to 0.5725. In case of using those mechanisms, the noise standard deviation should be lowered, impacting the privacy achieved. These results indicate that while the asset is highly effective for both user and control plane threats, the optimal choice of DP noise mechanism is highly dependent on the use case. The framework's flexibility in supporting multiple noise types is therefore a key advantage, allowing for the selection of a configuration that provides the best privacy-utility trade-off for a given scenario.

3.3.5. Updates related to the first prototype

The major advancement relative to the first prototype is the creation and usage of the control plane data for detection. A novel dataset has been created upon realistic benign traffic profiles and attack profiles relative to an actual DoS attack against the AMF service in the UMU 5G infrastructure, and the asset demonstrated a highly accurate detection. In addition, several enhancements relative to detection performance have been achieved. On one hand, detection times per flow lowered from a mean of 61.5 milliseconds to just 1 millisecond. On the other hand, balanced accuracy rose from 92.35% to 94.85% on user plane attack detection, and values close to 100% have been achieved in control plane attack detection. Also, it is now demonstrated that integrating DP in the FL process had no significant impact in performance for the majority of the

noise adding mechanisms supported. Moreover, the set of supported noise adding mechanisms has been extended to support Laplacian, Uniform, Exponential and Salt & Pepper mechanisms in addition to only Gaussian.

3.4. Holistic Security and Privacy Framework - HSPF

3.4.1. Component Architecture

The Holistic Security and Privacy Framework (HSPF) framework is composed of three main components: (i) Aggregator, (ii) Collector, and (iii) Agent. The Aggregator corresponds to the main framework unit, which coordinates the Federated Training procedure and performs the management and distribution of the different ML models used for anomaly detection by the different federated agents.

The Collector component collects inbound and outbound network traffic passing through the primary network interface. This information is then coupled into flows and stored until it is classified. Then, the Agent, where the federated agent resides, is responsible for inferencing the stored data, and identifying the potential malicious flow. In addition, the Agent also performs federated training rounds periodically, aiming to keep the ML model up to date being suitable to detect network traffic anomalies into the ever-changing landscape of the network communications.

The HSPF implementation architecture, present in Figure 6, illustrates how the HSPF components integrate with any application adopted to a micro-services paradigm. Moreover, the HSPF architecture has been designed to minimise potential data breaches, thus tackling the data privacy and security issue, since the collected data is never shared with any component outside of the Application Pod.

Figure 6 HSPF Components Integration

3.4.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The HSPF has been designed in a way that with one deployment all the services required for it to provide network anomaly detection over any Application are deployed at once. As previously mentioned, the Collector component continuously collects network traffic, which is then shared with the co-located Agent, in charge of performing the analysis of the network traffic. The data is collected from the main network interface of the Application using the NFStream tool [23] in a combination with a custom plugin, so the final set of collected features is the same as the feature vector present in the CICIDS2017 dataset [24]. Such format has been adopted considering that this dataset is one of the reference datasets commonly found in the literature for the theme of network intrusion and anomaly detection, and also considering the need for common ground to enable post-hoc performance comparison between the implemented ML approach and already existent works (that also use this feature vector).

For better understanding, the full list of features considered by the HSPF is:

`['id', 'src_ip', 'src_port', 'dst_ip', 'dst_port', 'protocol', 'timestamp', 'udps.flow_duration', 'src2dst_packets', 'dst2src_packets', 'udps.totlen_fwd_pkts', 'udps.totlen_bwd_pkts', 'src2dst_max_ps', 'src2dst_min_ps', 'src2dst_mean_ps', 'src2dst_stddev_ps', 'dst2src_max_ps', 'dst2src_min_ps', 'dst2src_mean_ps', 'dst2src_stddev_ps', 'udps.flow_byts_s', 'udps.flow_pkts_s', 'udps.flow_iat_max', 'udps.flow_iat_mean', 'udps.flow_iat_min', 'udps.flow_iat_std', 'udps.fwd_iat_tot', 'src2dst_mean_piat_ms', 'src2dst_stddev_piat_ms', 'src2dst_max_piat_ms', 'src2dst_min_piat_ms', 'udps.bwd_iat_tot', 'dst2src_mean_piat_ms', 'dst2src_stddev_piat_ms', 'dst2src_max_piat_ms', 'dst2src_min_piat_ms', 'src2dst_psh_packets', 'dst2src_psh_packets', 'src2dst_urg_packets', 'dst2src_urg_packets', 'udps.fwd_header_len', 'udps.bwd_header_len', 'udps.fwd_pkts_s', 'udps.bwd_pkts_s', 'udps.pkt_len_min', 'udps.pkt_len_max', 'udps.pkt_len_mean', 'udps.pkt_len_std', 'udps.pkt_len_var', 'udps.fin_flag_cnt', 'udps.syn_flag_cnt', 'udps.rst_flag_cnt', 'udps.psh_flag_cnt', 'udps.ack_flag_cnt', 'udps.urg_flag_cnt', 'udps.cwe_flag_cnt', 'udps.ece_flag_cnt', 'udps.down_up_ratio', 'udps.pkt_size_avg',`

'udps.fwd_seg_size_avg', 'udps.bwd_seg_size_avg', 'udps.fwd_byts_b_avg', 'udps.fwd_pkts_b_avg', 'udps.fwd_blk_rate_avg', 'udps.bwd_byts_b_avg', 'udps.bwd_pkts_b_avg', 'udps.bwd_blk_rate_avg', 'udps.subflow_fwd_pkts', 'udps.subflow_fwd_byts', 'udps.subflow_bwd_pkts', 'udps.subflow_bwd_byts', 'udps.init_fwd_win_byts', 'udps.init_bwd_win_byts', 'udps.fwd_act_data_pkts', 'udps.fwd_seg_size_min', 'udps.active_mean', 'udps.active_std', 'udps.active_max', 'udps.active_min', 'udps.idle_mean', 'udps.idle_std', 'udps.idle_max', 'udps.idle_min', 'bidirectional_packets']

3.4.3. Attacks targeted

HSPF will be trained to detect and generate alerts for different kind of attacks. This training through datasets and simulated environments relates to attacks such as:

- DoS Hulk, DoS, DoS Slowloris, DoS Slowhttptest, DDoS;
- Scanning attacks, using the open-source utility Nmap;
- FTP-Patator, SSH-Patator;
- Bot, Brute Force, Web Attack, SQL Injections.

3.4.4. Final Results

The latest developments of the HSPF components focused on validating the different architectural blocks, namely on extensively validating the existent ML model. In addition, an initial implementation of Zero Knowledge Proof (ZKP) has been completed, as well as the development of a dedicated API for the integration between the HSPF and the MTD (detailed in Section 3.4.4.3). Also, a supervised ML approach has been added to the HSPF decision engine and the respective validation results are described in Section 3.4.4.4.

3.4.4.1. Validation of the existent ML model - Intermedium phase

To evaluate the performance of the HSPF detection module, the HSPF has been deployed next to the Mobitrust platform [25], a micro-services oriented application, where normal traffic was generated, collected, classified and used to train the autoencoder applied by the HSPF detection module.

Three types of attacks were simulated against the Mobitrust services: DDoS, Brute Force and SQL Injection. The first was conducted with the mqtt-stresser [26] tool and targeted the message-broker component, whilst the second and the third both targeted the mt-gateway component and were conducted with curl [27], recurring to a set of most common usernames and passwords, as well as to recurring commands attempted during SQL Injection.

Table 5 presents the results obtained by the HSPF detection module. The *sensitivity* achieved for the targeted components, message-broker and gateway, were of 95.83% and 100.00%. As for the remaining components, the detection mechanism correctly classified 93.35%, 87.62% and 87.64% of normal flows for the monitor, orchestrator and postgresql components, respectively.

Table 5 HSPF Performance Evaluation

Component	TP	TN	FP	FN
Gateway	2646	28640	4562	115
Message-Broker	4083	36046	3164	0
Monitor	0	17856	1274	0
Orchestrator	0	29961	3710	0
Postgresql	0	40237	5675	0

3.4.4.2. Zero Knowledge Proof

An authentication method based on ZKP is being developed to increase data security (Figure 7). This method allows two components (Aggregator and Agent) to share information without revealing its content, thus increasing data privacy and security throughout training rounds. With this method, the Aggregator and the Agent components can prove each other that are trusted and they are the same component all the time, by sending proof in each message. If the aggregator doesn't have an agent's signature, this agent doesn't start the federated training and can't send any more messages to Aggregator.

Figure 7 Zero Knowledge Proof Information Sharing

3.4.4.3. Federated Learning as a Service

For the integration with the MTD asset (present in Figure 8), a dedicated service was developed, which consists of an API that provides the characteristics of a federated approach from an aggregation point of view. In detail, this API provides endpoints supporting the following actions: (i) receive and aggregate model weights from different federated clients; (ii) download the aggregated model.

Moreover, the data provider functionality has also been incorporated into the HSPF components, also in the form of an API, which provides the following capabilities: (i) retrieve number of features; (ii) retrieve training data; (iii) retrieve testing data.

Figure 8 Integration with MTD Asset

3.4.4.4. Latest ML implementation

The latest ML implementation addition to the HSPF decision engine was the addition of the XGBoost algorithm, a supervised approach capable of distinguishing between different types of attacks, contributing to the efficiency and accuracy of this framework.

Table 6 presents the results achieved for the attacks present in the CIC-IDS2017 dataset.

Table 6 HSPF Performance Evaluation (Latest)

Class	TP	TN	FP	FN
BENIGN	1576	6690	7	24
Bot	390	7901	5	1
DDOS	999	7297	0	1
DoS Hulk	998	7285	12	2
DoS Slowhttptest	993	7297	0	7
DoS slowloris	999	7290	7	1
FTP-Patator	1000	7294	3	0
SSH-Patator	1000	7293	4	0
Brute Force	299	7990	5	3
SQL Injection	0	8293	0	4

3.4.5. Updates related to the first prototype

The final version of the HSPF counts with two key achievements when compared to the first prototype: support for multi-class classification (using supervised ML) and inclusion of three different PETs: Differential Privacy, Multi-Party Computation and Homomorphic Encryption. In addition, the collected data used to evaluate the HSPF, whose results are present in Section 3.4.4.1, has been made available publicly on dataport with the name "ONE-MS-I: A micro-services

		MS-I"	SSH-Patator Brute Force Sql Injection		Encryption Multi- party Computati on		
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3.6. AI-Driven Cyber-Physical Correlator (CPC)

The AI-Driven CPC plays a central role in RIGOROUS's real-time threat detection and mitigation architecture. It acts as the entry point for cybersecurity awareness by continuously monitoring system and network-level data across energy-related infrastructures. Designed to detect anomalies and forward alerts to decision-making modules, the CPC effectively bridges physical processes and digital defence mechanisms.

3.6.1. Component Architecture

The CPC follows a modular, microservice-based architecture that ensures scalability, upgradability, and efficient data processing. We can consider that it is composed of the following layers:

- Data ingestion layer: Captures traffic from various sources (e.g., Renewable Energy Source (RES) gateways, smart meters, RES_CUT controllers) using packet sniffers or system-level agents. It supports both raw Packet Capture (PCAP) ingestion and structured JSON flow messages.
- Feature extraction: CPC reads the information and makes predictions using Machine Learning algorithms. Extracts relevant statistical and protocol-level features (e.g., flow duration, entropy, SETPOINT_BINOUT variation) used to characterize the behavior of traffic. In case an anomaly is detected, the user is informed by an alert message that is shown in the dashboard.
- Anomaly detection engine: Integrates machine learning models trained in historical and synthetic datasets. The final implementation supports supervised learning for labeled anomaly types, unsupervised learning, and threshold based alerting.
- Alert manager: Converts detected anomalies into structured alerts using STIX 2.1-compatible JSON format. Alerts include metadata (flow ID, IPs, anomaly type, timestamp) and are forwarded to the AI-driven decision-making component (AID) via Kafka.

Figure 9 Functional architecture of Cyber-Physical Correlator

3.6.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The work and data flow for the CPC is depicted in the following sequence diagram in Figure 10:

Figure 10 CPC workflow

The component receives network traffic flow and has the ability to detect an anomaly and send corresponding messages to the AID. In our revised test case scenario, the CPC detects possible

threats by analysing the traffic flow of the network and transmits threats to the AI-driven decision-making through the CPC-AID interface in a STIX message format as shown in the indicative example in Table 8:

Table 8 STIX message format as input from CPC to AID

Field	Message Description
Request Schema	<pre> { "type": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "testbed": "STRING", "objects": [{ "type": "STRING", "spec_version": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "value": "STRING", "value_type": "STRING", "flow_id": "STRING", "source_ip": "STRING", "source_port": "STRING", "destination_ip": "STRING", "destination_port": "STRING", "flow_data": "STRING", "label": "STRING" }, { "type": "STRING", "spec_version": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "model_id": "STRING", "model_name": "STRING", "learning_type": "STRING", "flow_features": "STRING", "threshold": "STRING", "binary_class_accuracy": "STRING", "multi_class_accuracy": "STRING", "comparison_metric": "STRING", "framework": "STRING", "framework_version": "STRING", "collection_tool": "STRING", "collection_tool_version": "STRING", "training_timestamp": "STRING" }], { </pre>

	<pre>"type": "STRING", "spec_version": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "relationship_type": "STRING", "source_ref": "STRING", "target_ref": "STRING" } }]</pre>
Request Example	<pre>{ "type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--a9b8c7d6-e5f4-1234-abcd-ff2233445566", "testbed": "WINGS", "objects": [{ "type": "anomalies", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomalies--fd10aa20-bb33-4ccd-8899-ff1122334455", "created": "2025-04-11T15:25:00Z", "modified": "2025-04-11T15:25:00Z", "value": "8", "value_type": "false_data_injection", "flow_id": "flow-232198", "source_ip": "192.168.20.45", "source_port": "6023", "destination_ip": "192.168.20.99", "destination_port": "9000", "flow_data": "[06-07-2024 10:05:28 AM, 3, ??1, GFC1,PLC,PV,16,8,16,8.083,1,0]", "label": "anomaly" }, { "type": "model-result", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "model-result--7a8b9c00-dddd-4222-bbbb-ccddeeff0011", "created": "2025-04-11T15:25:02Z", "modified": "2025-04-11T15:25:02Z", "model_id": "model1", "model_name": "RandomForest", "learning_type": "supervised", "flow_features": "['HIST_TIME', 'DAILYSAVINGTIME_SK', DEVICE_B1_NAME', 'DEVICE_B2_NAME', 'DEVICE_B3_NAME', SCADA_B2_NAME, 'DEVICE_B3_NAME', 'RES_TYPE', 'LR_LFCMX', 'SETPOINT_BINOUT', 'SCADA_SETPOINT_FB', 'GROSS_VALUE, 'WINDC_ON, 'WINCSUSP']]", "threshold": "0.87", }] }</pre>

	<pre>"binary_class_accuracy": "0.95", "multi_class_accuracy": "0.91", "comparison_metric": "F1-score", "framework": "scikit learn", "framework_version": "v1.13", "collection_tool": "Kaggle", "collection_tool_version": "v1.2.0", "training_timestamp": "025-03-20T10:15:00Z" }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--54732f74-09f8-416d-82f6-4e55c47a5367", "created": "2025-04-11T15:25:02Z", "modified": "2025-04-11T15:25:02Z", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "model--30772ca8-067b-4f88-a45f- f5b8579c088c", "target_ref": "anomalies--1aa7d222-ccc9-4562-ba47- 2b17bf9efd86" }] }</pre>
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Once the STIX messages are received and processed by AID, Response Mitigation (RM) functionality of the AID will generate one of the below mitigation actions within a Medium Security Policy Language (MSPL) policy as illustrated in section 4.2.4.

3.6.3. Attacks targeted

The attacks targeted by the CPC cover a range of cyber threats that affect both the cyber and physical dimensions of utility networks. These include:

- **Code and data injection attacks** involve the malicious alteration of control values (e.g., SETPOINT_BINOUT = 9999) or the injection of harmful command sequences into REST API calls or device-to-controller communications. These actions aim to disrupt the RES logic and the energy curtailment decision-making process by mimicking valid data ranges or targeting control signals exchanged between the RES, the RES_CUT application/controller, and the gateway. Such attacks can result in false curtailment decisions, privilege escalation, or the execution of unauthorized commands. As a mitigation measure, the CPC analyzes network traffic for anomalies and raises alerts, while AI-based Security Orchestration (SO) mechanisms actively block malicious traffic.
- **Distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks** targeting the RES_CUT application/controller or gateway, causing network congestion and service disruption. There is detection of abnormal packet rates targeting critical services resulting service degradation. As a mitigation measure, CPC monitors network traffic and identifies patterns indicative of DDoS. AI-driven decision-making prioritizes mitigation measures, while SO enforces traffic

filtering and rate limiting to drop excessive or suspicious requests before overwhelming the system.

3.6.4. Final Results

The evaluation of the updated classification model within the CPC demonstrates strong overall performance, indicating that the system is well-suited for real-time intrusion detection in the RIGOROUS context. The core metrics used—**accuracy**, **precision**, **recall**, and **F1-score**—are all in the vicinity of 89–90% as show in Table 9, which reflects a well-calibrated model.

- **Accuracy (89.03%)** represents the proportion of total correct predictions, including both attack and normal traffic classes. This figure confirms the model's overall reliability in varied operational scenarios.
- **Recall (89.03%)** shows that nearly 9 out of 10 actual attack cases were successfully identified. This is critical in intrusion detection systems, as failing to detect a genuine threat (false negative) can result in security breaches.
- **Precision (90.07%)** reveals that most attack predictions were accurate, minimizing false alarms (false positives). High precision is essential for reducing unnecessary mitigation efforts or alert fatigue among operators.
- **F1-Score (89.27%)**, as a harmonic mean of precision and recall, offers a balanced measure, reinforcing that the classifier maintains a good trade-off between catching attacks and avoiding false positives.

Table 9 Results of CPC classification model

Metric	Value
Accuracy	89.03%
Recall	89.03%
Precision	90.07%
F1-Score	89.27%

The confusion matrix provides further insight into class-wise performance:

- Normal traffic is classified with high confidence—3,584 instances were correctly identified, and very few were mistakenly flagged as attacks. This reduces the risk of false alerts on benign behaviour, preserving operational efficiency.
- Generic attacks are also well-recognized, with 2,246 correct classifications, suggesting that the model is robust in detecting commonly known patterns.
- DoS vs. Exploits: A significant level of misclassification is observed between DoS and Exploit attacks. Specifically, 383 DoS instances were wrongly labelled as Exploits, and 185 Exploits were interpreted as DoS. This likely stems from overlapping traffic characteristics (e.g., abrupt rate spikes or port scans) that confuse the model.
- Reconnaissance and Fuzzers show moderate confusion with each other and with Exploits. These attack types often involve probing or boundary testing behaviour that can resemble benign exploratory traffic or other subtle attacks, making them harder to distinguish reliably.
- Rare attack classes such as Worms, Backdoor, and Shellcode are frequently misclassified. This is expected due to class imbalance in the training data—these categories had far fewer samples, which limits the model's ability to generalize their distinct patterns.

The detailed matrix is described in the following Figure 11:

Figure 11 CPC confusion matrix

The CPC’s detection performance is overall effective, particularly for high-frequency and high-impact attacks. However, future improvements could focus on:

- Data augmentation or resampling techniques to balance rare classes.
- Ensemble methods or specialized sub-models for ambiguous categories like DoS vs. Exploits.
- Feature engineering to extract more discriminative traffic characteristics for difficult-to-separate attacks.

3.6.5. Updates related to the first prototype

Compared to the first prototype described in Deliverable D4.2, several refinements have been introduced. The updated CPC models have been trained using complementary datasets sourced from real RES environments and enriched with newly extracted features. These enhancements allow the system to better handle a more diverse range of cyberattack types. In addition, data captured from the WINGS 5G testbed will be used to validate the model’s accuracy and generalization performance under realistic network conditions. Furthermore, the STIX message structures exchanged between the CPC and downstream components (such as the AI-Driven Decision-Making module) have been refactored to improve semantic clarity and ensure full compatibility with the message parser of the AID component—enhancing end-to-end interoperability within the security automation workflow. Kafka enables real-time stream processing, as it shifts from batch-based flow parsing to real-time ingestion and scoring using a stream-first design. Finally, all this work is successfully integrated into a real 5G-enabled smart grid scenario. The CPC now serves as a stable, intelligent correlation engine, capable of adapting to evolving threats and offering explainable alerts that drive actionable decisions in the RIGOROUS ecosystem.

4 COGNITIVE DECISION, AND SECURITY MANAGEMENT

4.1. Introduction

The "Cognitive Decision and Security Management" section addresses the critical need for intelligent, adaptive, and robust cybersecurity solutions in the context of emerging 6G network environments. The motivation behind this research lies in the increasing complexity and diversity of cyber threats, which require more than static rule-based systems to ensure timely and effective responses.

To meet this challenge, two core modules have been developed:

1. The AI Decision-Making Module.
2. The Threat Risk Assessment (TRA) Module.

The AI Decision-Making Module leverages supervised machine learning techniques to autonomously determine the optimal mitigation strategy for each specific threats and network conditions. It builds its response based on real-time, data inputs from anomaly detectors which report all the anomalies detected on the different networks. Complementing this, the TRA Module forms the foundation of a comprehensive security risk assessment framework that dynamically classifies all the threats while assigning a risk score for each instance, based on multi-source data input, and communicates final score with AI Decision making module to complete the mitigation action. TRA module includes both static and dynamic risk management tools.

Below sections will dive more in the description and the results of each module.

4.2. AI-driven Decision Making - AID / RM

4.2.1. Component Architecture

Figure 12 illustrates the functioning architecture of the AI-driven decision-making (AID) system. It incorporates multiple AI models (agents) that utilize reinforcement learning techniques. Among these agents, one is optimized for time, while the other focuses on minimizing risk factors. The AID is triggered when an anomaly is detected, and it receives the risk value associated with it and makes an optimum mitigation action for the SO.

Figure 12 AI-driven decision-making functional block

Internally the two agents make a recommendation using the ensemble machine learning approach, and a reward function that are used to train and give decisions accordingly (Figure 13).

Figure 13 AI-driven Response-Mitigator functional block

4.2.2. Objective Function used for the Reward of AI Driven Agents

The objective function that is used to calculate the objective function of the AI driven agents is given by the below equation.

$$J = \sum_{\forall \theta_c \in \mathbb{L}} \frac{\text{Current Risk Value}}{\beta_1 T^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c) + \beta_2 E^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c) + \beta_3 \Psi^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c)}$$

The denominator of the objective function gives the total cost associated where $T^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c)$ denotes the total cost related to time, $E^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c)$ denotes the total cost associated to the energy and $\Psi^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c)$ denotes the total cost associated with the monetary costs for each iteration of the agent. The numerator of the function denotes the safety of the network by calculating the Risk Value and Current Risk Value. The Risk Value is the maximum possible Risk Factor reduction, if all of the attacks were addressed. The Current Risk value gives the reduction in the risk that resulted from the applied countermeasures. It is calculated after the agent selects an action. The β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are weighting values associated with each cost. These would be selected according to the needs of the agent's objective function.

4.2.3. Training of AI Driven Agents

This section explains the policy decisions that are going to be produced by the agent 1 and agent 2 respectively. The AI driven agents are going to do the policy decisions using the reinforcement learning technique named Q-learning. The goal of the agents is to maximize the cumulative reward over time by interacting with their surroundings. The expected cumulative rewards that the agents can obtain in a particular state by executing a particular action is represented by the Q-value. The Q-values are stored in each state by using a table, often known as the Q-table. At the beginning, the agent acts randomly, and the Q-table is empty. The Q-values are updated by the agents based on observable rewards and transitions, as it explores the environment. Based on the reward function, Agent 1 would be optimized for the time. Agent 2 would be optimizing the risk reduction.

The main steps for the Q-learning algorithm are given below, that would be used for both the agents:

1. Initialize the Q-table with zeros or random values.
2. Observe the current state.
3. Using an exploration-exploitation strategy, such as epsilon greedy, choose an action.
$$\text{epsilon} = \text{epsilon}_{\min} + (\text{epsilon}_{\max} - \text{epsilon}_{\min}) * e^{-\text{decay} * \text{epoch}}$$
4. Take the chosen action, receive a reward, and transition to the next state.
5. Update the Q-value of the current state-action pair using the Q-learning update rule:

Where,

$Q(s,a)$ is the Q-value of state s and action a .

lr is the learning rate that controls the impact of new information.

$R(s,s'')$ is the reward received for acting a in state s .

γ (**gamma**) is the discount factor that balances immediate and future rewards.

$\max(Q(s',a'))$ is the maximum Q-value over all possible actions in the next states.

In case the agents have converged, or the iterations have finished the optimum countermeasure is selected and is proposed to the security orchestrator for the mitigation.

4.2.4. Data Monitoring and Data Services

Data flow and monitoring for the AID along with the surrounding nodes are depicted in the below sequence diagram shown in Figure 14 below:

Figure 14 AID sequence diagram

Input data to the AID are received as STIX messages, in which all the information of the anomalies are pulled, STIX message format is shown in the below Table 10, for both the schema and an example of actual parameters.

Table 10 STIX message format as input to AID

Field	Message description
Request Schema	<pre>{ "type": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "testbed": "STRING", "objects": [{ "type": "STRING", "spec_version": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "value": "STRING", "value_type": "STRING", "flow_id": "STRING", "source_ip": "STRING", "source_port": "STRING", "destination_ip": "STRING", "destination_port": "STRING", "flow_data": "STRING", "label": "STRING" }, { "type": "STRING", "spec_version": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "model_id": "STRING", "model_name": "STRING", </pre>

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	<pre>"learning_type": "STRING", "flow_features": "STRING", "threshold": "STRING", "binary_class_accuracy": "STRING", "multi_class_accuracy": "STRING", "comparison_metric": "STRING", "framework": "STRING", "framework_version": "STRING", "collection_tool": "STRING", "collection_tool_version": "STRING", "training_timestamp": "STRING" }, { "type": "STRING", "spec_version": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "relationship_type": "STRING", "source_ref": "STRING", "target_ref": "STRING" }]</pre>
Request Example	<pre>{ "type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--cd2a2cf9-18f3-480a-aaa5-c4b59ce6910b", "testbed": "ONE", "objects": [{ "type": "anomalies", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomalies--1aa7d222-ccc9-4562-ba47-2b17bf9efd86", "created": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.870753Z", "modified": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.870753Z", "value": "1.45", "value_type": "reconstruction_error", "flow_id": "1", "source_ip": "20.1.249.77", "source_port": "61771", "destination_ip": "192.168.0.2", "destination_port": "80", "flow_data": "[4, 0, 4, 0, 248, 248, 1672.74, 0]", "label": "anomaly" }, { "type": "model",</pre>

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HC

	<pre>"spec_version": "2.1", "id": "model--30772ca8-067b-4f88-a45f-f5b8579c088c", "created": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.940615Z", "modified": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.940615Z", "model_id": "model1", "model_name": "MLP", "learning_type": "supervised", "flow_features": "['SrcPkts', 'DstPkts', 'TotPkts', 'DstBytes', 'SrcBytes', 'TotBytes', 'SrcLoad', 'DstLoad', '...']", "threshold": "1.20", "binary_class_accuracy": "99.70", "multi_class_accuracy": "99.70", "comparison_metric": "softmax", "framework": "tensorflow", "framework_version": "v0.2.1", "collection_tool": "nfstream", "collection_tool_version": "v0.6.0", "training_timestamp": "1921290190290" }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--54732f74-09f8-416d-82f6-4e55c47a5367", "created": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.963371Z", "modified": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.963371Z", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "model--30772ca8-067b-4f88-a45f-f5b8579c088c", "target_ref": "anomalies--1aa7d222-ccc9-4562-ba47-2b17bf9efd86" }]</pre>
--	--

Once the STIX messages are received and processed by AID, RM functionality of the AID will generate one of the below mitigation actions within an MSPL policy, Table 11, based on many factors, and parameters, which will be explained in the next section, 4.2.3.

Table 11 Mitigation actions

Mitigation action	Policy example
Network slicing	<pre>Create slice <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?> <ITResourceOrchestration xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" id="omsp1_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9"</pre>

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```
xsi:schemaLocation="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-
beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd mspl.xsd">
    <ITResource          id="mspl_9e9dbbdfad5d4ef588fc5ec579f83c59"
orchestrationID="omspl_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9">
    <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration">
        <capability>
            <Name>Network_slicing</Name>
        </capability>
        <configurationRule>
            <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="NetworkSlicingAction">
                <NetworkSlicingActionType>CREATE</NetworkSlicingActionType>
            </configurationRuleAction>
            <configurationCondition xsi:type="NetworkSlicingCondition">
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                <qosCondition>
                    <isCNF>>false</isCNF>
                    <priority>1</priority>
                    <maxBandwidth>10000000</maxBandwidth>
                    <minBandwidth>1000000</minBandwidth>
                </qosCondition>
                <networkSlicingConditionParameters>
                    <isCNF>>false</isCNF>
                    <SliceName>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING1.sql</SliceName>
                    <point>
                        <isCNF>>false</isCNF>
                        <dpid>05DAB551</dpid>
                        <dpid>05DAB551</dpid>
                    </point>
                    <SliceLocation>FE9B4176-14A9EFCC</SliceLocation>
                </networkSlicingConditionParameters>
            </configurationCondition>
        </configurationRule>
    </configuration>
</ITResource>
```


	<pre><Name>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING.sql</Name> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> </configurationRule> <Name>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING.sql</Name> </configuration> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration></pre>
Federated learning	<pre><?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?> <ITResourceOrchestration xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" id="omsp1_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" xsi:schemaLocation="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd mspl.xsd"> <ITResource id="mspl_9e9dbbdfad5d4ef588fc5ec579f83c59" orchestrationID="omsp1_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" > <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration"> <capability> <Name>fl_agent</Name> </capability> <configurationRule> <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="FederatedLearningRuleAction"> <federationLearnigActionType>AGENT</federationLearnigActionType> </configurationRuleAction> <configurationCondition xsi:type="FLConfigurationCondition"> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <instanceThreshold>100000</instanceThreshold> <aggregatorParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <URL>localhost:3333</URL> <apiPort>9090</apiPort> </aggregatorParameters></pre>

Fu


```
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  <apiPort>9999</apiPort>
</localConnectionParameters>
<integrationFabricParameters>
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    <topic>
      <isCNF>>false</isCNF>
      <purpose>training-flows-inffo</purpose>
      <name>training-flows-inffo</name>
    </topic>
  </topics>
</integrationFabricParameters>
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  <learningType>unsupervised</learningType>
  <modelParameters>
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    <subtype>autoencoder</subtype>
    <additionalParameters>
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      <decoderLayers>2</decoderLayers>
      <encoderNeurons>32-16</encoderNeurons>
      <decoderNeurons>16-32</decoderNeurons>
    </additionalParameters>
  <codeNeurons>8</codeNeurons>
  <lossFunction>mean-squared-error</lossFunction>
</additionalParameters>
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```
</modelParameters>
</learningModelInfo>
<learningParameters>
  <isCNF>false</isCNF>
  <testSize>0.33</testSize>
  <localEpochs>1</localEpochs>
  <batchSize>32</batchSize>
  <stepsPerEpoch>1</stepsPerEpoch>
</learningParameters>
<obfuscationInfo>
  <isCNF>false</isCNF>
  <technique>differential-privacy</technique>
  <parameters>
    <isCNF>false</isCNF>
    <mechanism>laplace-truncated</mechanism>
    <additionalParameters>
      <isCNF>false</isCNF>
      <epsilon>1.0</epsilon>
      <delta>0.0</delta>
    </additionalParameters>
  </parameters>
</obfuscationInfo>
</configurationCondition>
<externalData xsi:type="Priority">
  <value>60000</value>
</externalData>
<Name>Rule0</Name>
<isCNF>false</isCNF>
</configurationRule>
<Name>Conf0</Name>
</configuration>
<enablerCandidates>
```


	<pre><enabler>fl</enabler> </enablerCandidates> <orchestrationRequirements> <deploy>true</deploy> </orchestrationRequirements> <enforcementRequirements> <enforcementDomains> <domainID>Edge1</domainID> </enforcementDomains> </enforcementRequirements> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration></pre>
Firewall	<pre><?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?> <ITResourceOrchestration xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" id="omspl_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" xsi:schemaLocation="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd mspl.xsd"> <ITResource id="mspl_9e9dbbdfad5d4ef588fc5ec579f83c59" orchestrationID="omspl_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9"> <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration"> <capability> <Name>Firewall</Name> </capability> <configurationRule> <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="FirewallRuleAction"> <firewallActionType>DROP</firewallActionType> </configurationRuleAction> <configurationCondition xsi:type="FirewallConfigurationCondition"> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <ruleParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF></pre>

	<pre><destinationAddress>0.0.0.0</destinationAddress> <action>drop</action> <sourceAddress>192.168.0.0</sourceAddress> <name>ejemplo1</name> </ruleParameters> </configurationCondition> <externalData xsi:type="Priority"> <value>60000</value> </externalData> <Name>Rule0</Name> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> </configurationRule> <Name>Conf0</Name> </configuration> <enablerCandidates> <enabler>firewall</enabler> </enablerCandidates> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration></pre>
Command and control	<pre><configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration"> <capability> <Name>commandControl</Name> </capability> <configurationRule> <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="CommandControlRuleAction"> <commandControlActionType>CAMERA</commandControlActionType> </configurationRuleAction> <configurationCondition xsi:type="CommandControlConfigurationCondition"> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <cameraRuleParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> </cameraRuleParameters> </configurationCondition> </configurationRule> </configuration></pre>

	<pre><request>true</request> <action>stop</action> <macAddress>00:00:00:00:00</macAddress> <command_id>1234567890</command_id> </cameraRuleParameters> </configurationCondition> </configurationRule> <Name>Conf0</Name> </configuration> <enablerCandidates> <enabler>camera</enabler> </enablerCandidates></pre>
SIEM	<pre><?xml version='1.0' encoding='UTF-8' standalone='yes'?> <ITResourceOrchestration id="omsp1_46bdc9a9035540d4b257bd686a7e6bc5" xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618- beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"> <ITResource id="mspl_47bdc9a9035540d4b257bd686a7e6c54" orchestrationID="omsp1_47bdc9a9035540d4b257bd686a7e6bc5"> <configuration xsi:type='RuleSetConfiguration'> <capability> <Name>Network_traffic_analysis</Name> </capability> <configurationRule> <configurationRuleAction xsi:type='MonitoringAction'> <monitoringActionType>ALERT</monitoringActionType> <correlationRules> <filename>incibe_dos.xml</filename> <!--> Común a ambas </!--> <group>cerberus_snort</group> <!--> Común a ambas </!--> </correlationRules> </configurationRuleAction> </configurationRule> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration></pre>


```
<id>444443</id>
<level>10</level>
<description>Snort Event ID 20101 with RuleId
1000020: Possible DoS Flood TCP Syn</description>
</correlationRule>
</correlationRules>
</configurationRuleAction>
<configurationCondition
xsi:type='MonitoringConfigurationConditions'>
  <monitoringConfigurationCondition>
    <SiemCorrelations>
      <SiemCorrelation>
        <correlationRuleId>444443</correlationRuleId>
        <agentEventRule>20100</agentEventRule>
        <!--> Cuando hay más de uno, se traduce a <if_sid>20100, 20101</if_sid> <!-->
        <agentEventRule>20101</agentEventRule>
        <agentRuleId>1000020</agentRuleId>
      </SiemCorrelation>
    </SiemCorrelations>
  </monitoringConfigurationCondition>
</configurationCondition>
<Name>Rule_wazuh_333333</Name>
</configurationRule>
<Name>Conf_333333</Name>
</configuration>
<priority>1000</priority>
<enablerCandidates>
  <enabler>wazuh</enabler>
</enablerCandidates>
</ITResource>
</ITResourceOrchestration>
```

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Telemetry	<pre><?xml version='1.0' encoding='UTF-8' standalone='yes'?> <ITResourceOrchestration id="omspl_46bdc9a9035540d4b257bd686a7e6bc3" xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618- beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xsi:schemaLocation="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d- 425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd mspl.xsd"> <ITResource id="mspl_46bdc9a9035540d4b257bd686a7e6c55" orchestrationID="omspl_46bdc9a9035540d4b257bd686a7e6bc5"> <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration"> <capability> <Name>Telemetry</Name> </capability> <configurationRule> <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="TelemetryAction"> <telemetryActionType>TRANSFER</telemetryActionType> </configurationRuleAction> <configurationCondition xsi:type="TransferConfigurationConditions"> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <transferConfigurationCondition> <domainID>liqo-Ireland</domainID> <flavorID>k8sliqo0</flavorID> </transferConfigurationCondition> <exporterEndpoint>http://10.208.99.108:30000/api/v1/write</exporterEndpoint> </configurationCondition> <Description>Transfer metrics from cluster UMU (flavorID k8sliqo0) to IBM</Description> <Name>Transfer01</Name> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> </configurationRule> <Name>Conf1</Name> </configuration> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration> </pre></pre>
-----------	--

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HC

	<pre><priority>1000</priority> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration></pre>
Channel protection	<pre><?xml version='1.0' encoding='UTF-8' standalone='yes'?> <ITResourceOrchestration id="omspl_46bdc9a9035540d4b257bd686a7e6bc3" xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618- beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xsi:schemaLocation="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d- 425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd mspl.xsd"> <ITResource id="mspl_46bdc9a9035540d4b257bd686a7e6c31" orchestrationID="omspl_46bdc9a9035540d4b257bd686a7e6bc3"> <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration"> <capability> <Name>channel_protection</Name> </capability> <configurationRule> <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="ChannelProtectionRuleAction"> <channelProtectionActionType>PROACTIVE</channelProtectionActionType> </configurationRuleAction> <configurationCondition xsi:type="ChannelProtectionConfigurationCondition"> <spd> <localAddress>192.168.157.68</localAddress> <remoteAddress>192.168.157.70</remoteAddress> <modeType>TRANSPORT</modeType> <sad> <encryptionAlgorithm>aes</encryptionAlgorithm> <encryptionKey1>key1</encryptionKey1> <encryptionKey2>key2</encryptionKey2> <enclv>keyenc</enclv></pre>

```
<integrityAlgorithm>md5</integrityAlgorithm>
<intKey1>keyint1</intKey1>
<intKey2>keyint2</intKey2>
<softByte>512</softByte>
<softPackets>20</softPackets>
<softAdded>64</softAdded>
<softUsed>1024</softUsed>
<hardByte>1024</hardByte>
<hardPackets>10</hardPackets>
<hardAdded>128</hardAdded>
<hardUsed>2048</hardUsed>
  </sad>
</spd>
</configurationCondition>
<externalData xsi:type="Priority">
  <value>60000</value>
</externalData>
<Name>Rule0</Name>
<isCNF>false</isCNF>
</configurationRule>
<Name>Conf0</Name>
</configuration>
<enablerCandidates>
  <enabler>channel_protection</enabler>
</enablerCandidates>
</ITResource>
</ITResourceOrchestration>
```

4.2.5. Final Results

In this section, we will describe the core functionalities and working principles of the AI Decision making module within the whole FuelSOME toolkit, from security management framework. as

described earlier, AID is responsible for dynamically evaluating cyber threats and propose the optimal mitigation action to be performed based on predefined constraints and real time input from anomaly detectors.

The AID module using q learning based simulations will optimize the response in face of cyberattacks, through two different agents, the safety agent and the time efficiency agent.

The key operational parameters on which the AID relies on for generating the response are:

1. Mitigation budget, or cost for each countermeasure.
2. Attack risk, which is a dynamic score associated with each attack, calculated and assigned by the TRA module.
3. User defined constraints, internal to the AID, that serve as an input for the internal AID process. These include the total available budget, the minimum acceptable safety level and the required risk reduction level.

Once the AID receives and initializes all the input parameters needed for its operation, it runs multiple simulations, referred as episodes, in which it tests various combinations of countermeasures against the detected anomalies. By using the reward function, the AID agents help to get optimum mitigation action against the anomalies. Each episode's results are stored in a matrix mapping attack types to countermeasures, and the optimum episode is selected that satisfy the below mentioned conditions:

1. Stays within budget
2. Meets or exceeds the minimum safety level defined initially
3. Achieves the desired level of risk reduction that is set

To make the above operational process easier and clearer, below is an example on what is exactly happening.

Suppose that the following hyperparameters are initially given to the AID module:

- Budget: 150, which is the needed from the system administrator, and this value once decided is going to be static during the whole process
- Minimum safety level: 98%, again based on the system administrator's decision
- Minimum risk reduction: 95%

Using the above values as inputs, the AID initiates a series of episodes. In each one, different sets of countermeasures are applied against detected anomalies. The output of each episode is a matrix that map the countermeasures to the different anomalies as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Selected countermeasure against the anomalies

Figure 16 below shows the summarized output of the AID showing the optimal episode and the corresponding countermeasures that were selected. As seen in Figure 16 each episode is compared using the total rewards it achieved, the budget it used, and the final risk achieved. The final optimum episode is thus selected, and the corresponding optimal mitigation action is sent as an MSPL policy to the SO.

	Risk Reduction	Matches Matrix	Optimal
14	1.000000	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	True
0	1.000000	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
15	1.000000	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
1	0.987654	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
2	0.987654	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
11	0.987654	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
5	0.987654	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, ...	False
13	0.975309	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, ...	False
8	0.975309	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
6	0.975309	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, ...	False
12	0.975309	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, ...	False
3	0.975309	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
7	0.975309	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
18	0.975309	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
4	0.975309	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, ...	False
19	0.962963	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
16	0.962963	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, ...	False
17	0.962963	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
9	0.962963	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False
10	0.930617	[[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0, ...	False

Figure 16 Episodes list

4.2.6. Updates related to the first prototype

Phase 1 testing of RIGOUROUS platform was finalized and all results for the 6 test cases defined under the phase 1 scope were reported in deliverable D5.2 "Platform prototype integration and In-Lab testing 2" [5].

AID/RM was a major component of most of the test cases, with common flow of information, as depicted in Figure 17 below:

Figure 17 Data flow with AID module

Once the anomalies are received by the AID, through the STIX messages registered in Kafka, under the topic R12-AID-TRA, as shown in the Figure 18 below, internal agents of AID will be triggered as explained by the previous section 4.2.2.

```
2025-01-08 09:26:02,567 [INFO] Consumed message ID: bundle--209374a3-25ff-4baa-8791-914ae0e0a543 From ONE  
  
2025-01-08 09:29:13,036 [INFO] Consumed message ID: bundle--317216da-92e5-4ae7-bbb3-f676dc53e9f3 From ONE
```

Figure 18 STIX message received by AID

Next, AID will look for the risk score of the anomalies from the AID-TRA topic under Kafka, by mapping the unique ID of each anomaly, and trigger the internal process to generate the optimum mitigation action based on all the input received.

Once the mitigation action is finalized, AID will send an MSPL policy directly to the SO, as shown in Figure 19 below:

```
?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?>  
ITResourceOrchestration xmlns="http://modellosoft.com/xsd/designer/a22b00b-ee3d-425c-8618-bbb6a854851a/ITResource.xsd"  
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" id="omsp_5b0f47359a540f6e02390710c1152ed9" xsi:schemaLocation="http://modellosoft.com/xsd/designer/a22b00b-  
ee3d-425c-8618-bbb6a854851a/ITResource.xsd msp.xsd"/>  
<ITResource id="mspl_94b0b0fa5d6af588f54c579f83c59" orchestrationId="omsp_5b0f47359a540f6e02390710c1152ed9">  
  <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration">  
    <capability>  
      <name>Firewall</name>  
    </capability>  
    <configurationRule>  
      <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="FirewallRuleAction">  
        <firewallActionType>DROP</firewallActionType>  
      </configurationRuleAction>  
      <configurationCondition xsi:type="FirewallConfigurationCondition">  
        <isCOP>false</isCOP>  
        <ruleParameters>  
          <isCOP>false</isCOP>  
          <destinationAddress>0.0.0.0</destinationAddress>  
          <actionDrop/>  
          <sourceAddress>192.168.0.0</sourceAddress>  
          <name>mspl1</name>  
        </ruleParameters>  
      </configurationCondition>  
      <externalData xsi:type="Priority">  
        <value>0000</value>  
      </externalData>  
      <name>Rule0</name>  
      <isCOP>false</isCOP>  
    </configurationRule>  
  </configuration>  
  <enablerCandidates>  
    <enabler>Firewall</enabler>  
  </enablerCandidates>  
</ITResource>  
</ITResourceOrchestration>
```

Figure 19 Mitigation action sent by AID

To measure the effectiveness of the AID within the whole workflow, many KPIs were selected based on the maturity of the system during the phase 1, accordingly the below 3 KPIs in Table 12 were selected and measured during the tests.

Table 12 KPIs for measuring the AID performance during tests

KPI #	Description
KPI-16	Number of kinds of Cyberattacks detected through AI > 10
KPI-20	Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA
KPI-21	Improve decision-making on threat mitigation by 45% compared to SOTA

The below values shown in Table 13 were recorded during the live and real tests performed, in the 6 test cases. We will show the range of values measured compared to the target value that we aim to reach by end of the project.

Table 13 measured valued of the KPIs

KPI #	Measured Value	Target Value
KPI-16	1 to 2 attacks	>10
KPI-20	3.5 to 70 seconds	<240 seconds
KPI-21	2.5 to 36 seconds	<60 seconds

As witnessed in the above table, all the KPIs were below the target value, which shows a great maturity of the AID in processing the data and generating the optimum response, except for the KPI-16 which was foreseen to be between 1 and 2 during prototype 1, since the consortium agreed to show the RIGOUROUS behaviour for just 1 attack at a time, knowingly that AID is capable to process more attacks simultaneously and process them concurrently as explained in simulations.

4.3. Threat Risk Assessor - TRA

4.3.1. Component Architecture

Figure 20 TRA component architecture

As depicted in Figure 20, the **{TRA}** service receives the **{Threat Notification}** information as subscribed Topics published by the Kafka broker and fetches contextual and threat information from the fabric **{CTI, System Model}** to assess the actual Level of Risk based using Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS).

The points below provide high level information regarding the relevant key topics associated with the bold and bracketed terms:

- [TRA] receives the Threat notification as Kafka messages (topic R12-AID-TRA).
- [TRA] receives either from RIGOUROUS fabric (System Model) or from external resource(s) the characteristics (HW, SW, operation, etc.) of the [ASSET] or [RESOURCE] targeted by the attack notified by the AID or potentially compromised during its execution.
- The structured **{System Model}** characterises assets or resources (see Annex 1) including:
 - End user device, application or resource hardware and software description,
 - Network interfaces characterisation,
 - User information (authentication credential, access level, capabilities, etc.),
 - Connections and flow definition.
- The completeness of the targeted asset or resource characterisation is a best effort service, expected information may not be available to fabric.
- The TRA shall also rely on default backup parameters when one or more field of the system model is not defined,

- The TRA shall provide a risk score even when the targeted asset/resource is unknown or not fully characterised through the system model.
- The contextual **{Cyber Threat Intelligence}** knowledge (threat definition, CTI, Common vulnerability databases etc.) is retrieved from a publish/subscribe messaging service instantiated by RIGOUROUS framework (Kafka). Alternatively, it can be retrieved from external vulnerability repositories such as:
 - The NIST National Vulnerability Data Base [28]
 - The MITRE Common Vulnerability & Exposure [29]
- Given the **{Cyber Threat Intelligence}** (threat identification, threat type) and the exploitable vulnerabilities corresponding to the **{System Model}** of the asset or resource under attack, the [TRA] establishes the potential impact (severity) of the Threat.
- The [TRA] processes the information and returns to the Kafka broker (TOPIC TRA-AID) a level of risk = {Risk Score} as per the CVSS.
- TRA shall support CVSS V3.1 as baseline.

4.3.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The TRA has only one input/incoming interface corresponding with the R12-AID-TRA Kafka broker topic. Through this interface, the module consumes all anomaly messages that require risk assessment and assigns a corresponding risk score for each event. It concerns all testbeds and all the use cases. All the components interested in consuming the all or part of the information contained in the risk score TRA produced message can access it through a unique output/outgoing interface: the TRA-AID topic. The schema and some examples of the risk score message are illustrated in Figure 21 and Table 14.

Figure 21 TRA sequence diagram

4.3.3. Final Results

During the second prototype phase, the TRA was successfully deployed to process a subset of anomaly messages across several testbeds. The most advanced integration was achieved in the ORO use case (Use Case 1), where the system model was mapped to the testbed's assets and network topology. This enabled the TRA to correlate anomalies with specific assets and retrieve Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE)-based vulnerability information. For example, the

following CVE-based risk score was produced for a critical Remote Code Execution vulnerability in Nokia AMS (CVE-2022-41763, CVSS 8.8):

Table 14 TRA Response schema and some examples retrieved from various testbeds. Both heuristic and CVE-based risk score evaluations are depicted

Field	Message Description
TRA Risk Score Response Schema	<pre> { "type": "STRING", "spec_version": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "risk-score": { "anomalies--1": [{ "cve_id": "STRING", "cpe": "STRING", "description": "STRING", "cvss31_vector_string": "STRING", "base_score": FLOAT, "base_severity": "STRING", "attack_vector": "STRING", "attack_complexity": "STRING", "privileges_required": "STRING", "user_interaction": "STRING", "confidentiality_impact": "STRING", "integrity_impact": "STRING", "availability_impact": "STRING" }] } } </pre>
TRA Risk Score Response Example 1 CVE Based Score ORO testbed	<pre> { "type": "risk_score", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "bundle--cd2a2cf9-18f3-480a-aaa5-c4b59ce6910b", "created": "2025-06-02 09:32:43.927186522", "modified": "2025-06-02 09:32:43.927193422", "risk-score": { "anomalies--1": [{ "cve_id": "CVE-2022-41763", "cpe": "cpe:2.3:a:nokia:access_management_system:9.7.05:*:*:*:*:*:*:*:", "description": "An issue was discovered in NOKIA AMS 9.7.05. Remote Code Execution exists via the debugger of the ipAddress variable...", </pre>

	<pre>"cvss31_vector_string": "CVSS:3.1/AV:N/AC:L/PR:L/UI:N/S:U/C:H/I:H/A:H", "base_score": 8.8, "base_severity": "HIGH", "attack_vector": "NETWORK", "attack_complexity": "LOW", "privileges_required": "LOW", "user_interaction": "NONE", "confidentiality_impact": "HIGH", "integrity_impact": "HIGH", "availability_impact": "HIGH" }] }</pre>
TRA Risk Score Response Example 2 Heuristic Score ONE testbed	<pre>{ "type": "risk_score", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "bundle--94de5219-eb02-4953-bfe5-b7d6ef0863b6", "created": "2025-06-02T09:28:14.345556005", "modified": "2025-06-02T09:28:14.345558005", "risk_score": { "anomalies--0e8cf689-a5db-4ee2-b8fd-4bd604a075a9": 2 }, "user_data_impact": null, "description": null }</pre>
TRA Risk Score Response Example 3 Heuristic Score WINGS testbed	<pre>{ "type": "risk_score", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "bundle--c4e8ab0c-d31f-4380-a08e-2bc8fedbb6b3", "created": "2025-06-02T09:28:48.039130796", "modified": "2025-06-02T09:28:48.039133696", "risk_score": { "anomalies--f6b1061e-dac5-49c7-b42d-3a2ba457a88c": 1, "anomalies--425c9118-1824-4ae5-8064-23bf59cc88c7": 1 }, "user_data_impact": null, "description": null }</pre>

In contrast, other testbeds such as ONE and WINGS have not yet integrated a mapped system model. In these cases, the TRA used the earlier heuristic-based method to compute basic risk scores from anomalies alone.

These results highlight the functional maturity of the CVE-based approach in ORO and demonstrate the foundational readiness of the heuristic-based fallback for testbeds where asset

mapping is still pending. Moving forward, completing the system model integration across all testbeds will enable the TRA to deliver consistent, context-aware risk evaluations.

4.3.4. Updates related to the first prototype

The second prototype of the TRA introduces significant enhancements over the initial version. While the first prototype relied on a semi-dummy heuristic to estimate a risk score solely based on anomaly data detected by the anomaly-detectors within a given use case, the updated version now incorporates a more structured and context-aware approach. The TRA now consumes a system model (`system-model.yaml`), conforming to the described in D3.2) that defines the assets and their roles within the system's network topology. This advancement allows the TRA to correlate incoming anomalies, formatted according to the STIXv2 JSON anomaly schema, defined by the R12-AID-TRA interface, with specific assets, retrieve relevant CVE and CVSS vulnerability information from internal or external databases (such as NIST NVD or MITRE CVE), and use this enriched context to calculate a more coherent and realistic risk score. This transformation aligns the TRA more closely with real-world threat assessment practices by grounding risk scores in both asset-specific vulnerabilities and the nature of the detected anomalies.

5 AI-DRIVEN SECURITY RESPONSE-MITIGATION

5.1. Introduction

The proliferation of IoT devices has revolutionized the way modern utilities operate, enabling smart grids, real-time monitoring, and automated control. However, this digital transformation introduces an extensive and heterogeneous attack surface. Traditional security mechanisms struggle to keep up with the scale, complexity, and dynamism of IoT environments, particularly in energy-critical infrastructures. The limitations of conventional approaches—manual threat detection, delayed response, and static rule sets—render them ineffective against increasingly sophisticated cyber threats such as DDoS, False Data Injection (FDI), and advanced exploitation of IoT protocol mismatches.

To address these challenges, the RIGOUROUS project integrates AI as a core enabler for proactive and intelligent mitigation of cyberattacks. AI-powered mitigation tools developed within the project automate security responses, enabling near real-time containment and resolution of threats. These include the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator, which uses Deep Learning to forecast and block harmful resource scaling during application-layer DDoS attacks, and the DASC module, which detects and resolves policy or protocol mismatches across IoT communication chains. Complemented by simulations from the Digital Twin and recommendations from the AI-driven 6G Mitigation Engine, these tools collectively deliver a multi-layered, context-aware security framework tailored to the evolving needs of future energy and industrial networks.

5.2. AI-powered EDoS Mitigator

5.2.1. Component Architecture

As introduced in Deliverable D4.1 [1], the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator can proactively mitigate Economical Denial of Sustainability (EDoS) attacks by adopting a DL-powered forecasting-based approach for detecting malicious scaling requests caused by application-layer DDoS attacks. The asset's functional architecture has been presented in Deliverable D4.2, highlighting the key components of the asset, namely the Admission Controller, which intercepts the resource scaling requests to entrust their validation to EDoS Mitigator, and the EDoS Mitigator, which leverages a DL model to automatically discriminate malicious scaling requests. More details on the proposed DL model can be found in Deliverable D4.2 [2] and papers [10,11].

Figure 22 illustrates the developed components of the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator asset and their integration with Kubernetes (K8s)'s Horizontal Pod Autoscaler (HPA). All components are packaged as Docker images and deployed either as admission webhooks or services in K8s. The developed components consist of:

Figure 22 Deployment Architecture and Workflow of AI-powered EDoS Mitigator Asset

- **Admission Controller** – It is implemented as a **ValidatingWebhookConfiguration** [12] and configured to intercept scaling requests triggered by HPA for Video Streamer resource. The Admission Controller invokes the `/validate` endpoint of the HPA Validation Webhook to assess the legitimacy of the scaling request.
- **HPA Validation Webhook** – It represents the webhook API and is implemented as a Flask application. It exposes `/validate` endpoint to interface with the Admission Controller. Once a validation request is received, the HPA Validation Webhook forwards it to EDoS Mitigator to decide on legitimacy or maliciousness of the scaling request. This is achieved by invoking the `/api/v1/validate` endpoint of the EDoS Mitigator. If the EDoS Mitigator flags the scaling request as legitimate, HPA Validation Webhook informs the Admission Controller to authorize the scaling out operation. Otherwise, the scaling request is rejected and an anomaly report in STIX format is published to Kafka Broker to trigger further measures by AID to mitigate the attack.
- **EDoS Mitigator** – It is a Flask API that exposes two endpoints for detecting anomalies in resource usage and performance metrics using a DL-based anomaly detection model [10,11]. Indeed, the anomalies are detected when the predicted metrics' values drift considerably from the observed ones.
 - `/api/v1/fromcsv` – detects anomalies from an uploaded csv file.
 - `/api/v1/validate` – enables real-time anomaly detection from current data. To this end, it invokes the `/api/v1/get_k8s_metrics_csv` of the EDoS's Monitoring System to collect the current resource usage and performance metrics. More details on the EDoS's Monitoring System are provided in Section 5.2.2. This endpoint is the one invoked by the HPA Validation Webhook.

In addition, it exposes `/api/v1/metadata`, which returns metadata about the DL model used by the EDoS Mitigator.

Details of the implemented endpoints are provided in Section 5.2.2.

5.2.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

To collect data that can be used by the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator for training or during serving time, we implemented a “Monitoring System” that uses Prometheus API and different probes to extract the raw resource usage (e.g., CPU, memory, disk and network usage) and performance (e.g., response time) metrics from the virtual Content Delivery Network (vCDN) slices’ Cloud Native Functions (i.e., video streamer and cache). The metrics are collected as time series and returned in a CSV file or a JSON format. The initial implementation of the EDoS’s Monitoring System, presented in D4.2, has been updated to use Istio Service Mesh rather than NGINX-to-Prometheus log file exporter to collect performance metrics.

The Monitoring System offers the capabilities to generate on-demand datasets for training and testing the DL model, or to scrape real-time metrics values for use by the trained DL model integrated in EDoS Mitigator for forecasting-based anomaly detection.

The EDoS’s Monitoring System is developed using Flask, containerized as Docker image, and deployed as a K8s service. It exposes the following 4 POST endpoints:

- `/api/v1/get_k8s_metrics_csv` - collects all metrics and returns the results in a CSV file.
- `/api/v1/get_k8s_metrics_all` - collects all metrics and returns the results in a JSON format.
- `/api/v1/get_istio_metrics_csv` - collects only istio metrics and returns the results in a CSV file.
- `/api/v1/get_istio_metrics_all` - collects only istio metrics and returns the results in a JSON format.

Table 15 describes the request schema and an example of actual parameters for invoking the endpoints of the EDoS’s Monitoring System.

Table 15 Request Schema for EDoS’s Monitoring System

Field	Description
Request/Data Schema	<pre>{ "namespace": "string", "deployment": "string", "pod": "string", "container": "string", "start_time": "string", "end_time": "string", "step": "string", "period": "string" }</pre>
Request/Data Example	<pre>{ "namespace": "slice1", "deployment": "streamer-slice1-deployment", "pod": "streamer-slice1", "container": "streamer-slice1", "start_time": "2025-05-09 13:10:00", "end_time": "2025-05-09 13:30:00", "step": "1m", "period": "2m" }</pre>

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The `/validate` POST endpoint, exposed by the HPA Validation Webhook, handles the AdmissionReview request sent by the Admission Controller and sends back its decision as an AdmissionReview response. Readers can refer to K8s documentation for more information on the available attributes for admission requests and responses [13]. In our case, the HPA Validation Webhook extracts the fields "namespace", "app", and "deployment" from the received AdmissionReview request and uses them to invoke the `/api/v1/validate` endpoint of the EDoS Mitigator. The "allowed" and "status" attributes of the AdmissionResponse object are used to return the admission review decision. Table 16 illustrates the content of these two attributes in case of accepted and rejected scaling admission requests.

Table 16 Responses of /validate endpoint of HPA Validation Webhook

Field	Description
Accepted scaling request	{ "allowed": True, "status": "streamer-slice1: Scaling action authorized." }
Rejected scaling request	{ "allowed": False, "status": "streamer-slice1: Anomaly detected, scaling action not authorized." }

Table 17 presents the request schema along with an example of actual parameters used to invoke the EDoS Mitigator's `/api/v1/validate` endpoint. It presents also an example of the response returned by the endpoint. The response body contains the decision on whether an anomaly exists or not and provides the anomaly score.

Table 17 Request & Response Schema for EDoS Mitigator's /api/v1/validate endpoint

Field	Description
Request/Data Schema	{ "namespace": string, "deployment": string, "app": string }
Request/Data Example	{ "namespace": "slice1", "deployment": "streamer-slice1-deployment", "app": "streamer-slice1" }
Response Schema	{ "anomaly": bool, "msg": string }
Response Example	{ "anomaly": false, "msg": "No anomaly detected (-0.012215535156428814)" }

	}
--	---

When an anomaly is detected, the HPA Validation Webhook rejects the scaling request and publishes an anomaly report in STIXv2 format to R13-AID topic, to which AID is subscribed. The anomaly report is a STIX2's bundle containing two custom objects—"anomaly" and "model"—which conform to the data model presented in Table 18. The table presents also an example of an actual anomaly report generated by the HPA Validation Webhook.

Table 18 Data Model of Anomaly Report Generated by EDoS' HPA Validation Webhook

Field	Description
Request/Data Schema	<pre>{ "type": String, "id": String, "testbed": String, "objects": [{ "type": "anomaly", "spec_version": String, "id": String, "created": String, "modified": String, "namespace": String, "deployment": String, "app": String, "host_ip": String, "host_port": String, "upf_testbed": String, "anomaly_score": Float }, { "type": "model", "spec_version": String, "id": String, "created": String, "modified": String, "model_id": String, "model_name": String, "lookback": Integer, "normalize": Boolean, "scale_scores": Boolean, "anomaly_threshold": Float, "transformer": String, "n_features": Integer, "time_series_features": [String], "f1": Float, "precision": Float, "recall": Float, }] }</pre>

	<pre>"train_framework": String, "train_framework_version": String, "serve_framework": String, "serve_framework_version": String, "collection_tool": String, "collection_tool_version": String, "training_timestamp": Integer }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": String, "id": String, "created": String, "modified": String, "relationship_type": String, "source_ref": String, "target_ref": String }] }</pre>
Request/Data Example	<pre>{ "type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--d73b14cd-3696-4277-9bb5-bbaed9ccc306", "testbed": "oulu", "objects": [{ "type": "anomaly", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomaly--14c3faf7-921f-4d0f-9b14- 66b86710068e", "created": "2025-05-21T17:06:10.260582Z", "modified": "2025-05-21T17:06:10.260582Z", "namespace": "slice1", "deployment": "streamer-slice1-deployment", "app": "streamer-slice1", "host_ip": "192.168.0.10", "host_port": "30668", "upf_testbed": "oulu", "anomaly_score": 3.6625 }, { "type": "model", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "model--7b518d60-ffe7-4006-8f70-4a18955ae3c0", "created": "2025-05-21T17:06:10.261879Z", "modified": "2025-05-21T17:06:10.261879Z", "model_id": "s1S_03022022_085334", }] }</pre>

	<pre>"model_name": "CGATGRU", "lookback": 80, "normalize": true, "scale_scores": true, "anomaly_threshold": 0.5672, "transformer": "MinMax", "n_features": 12, "time_series_features": ["cpu_usage", "cpu_usage_sys", "cpu_usage_user", "http_requests_rate", ...], "f1": 92.61, "precision": 88.15, "recall": 97.54, "train_framework": "pytorch", "train_framework_version": "2.4.1", "serve_framework": "onnx", "serve_framework_version": "1.17.0", "collection_tool": "EDoS_Monitoring_System", "collection_tool_version": "v1", "training_timestamp": 1643888014 }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--74d02b23-e8c4-4db9-8e8c- bb8e8318c9d1", "created": "2025-05-21T17:06:10.262273Z", "modified": "2025-05-21T17:06:10.262273Z", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "model--7b518d60-ffe7-4006-8f70- 4a18955ae3c0", "target_ref": "anomaly--14c3faf7-921f-4d0f-9b14- 66b86710068e" }] }</pre>
--	---

5.2.3. Final Results

The AI-powered EDoS Mitigator asset has been integrated and its performance tested in a local testbed based on a K8s cluster set up on OULU's CSC OpenStack-based cloud⁴. Open5GS [14] and UERAN-SIM [15] are used to implement the 5G SA Core and simulate the 5G RAN and User Equipment (UEs), respectively. The simulated UEs are used to generate normal or malicious load. The conducted tests demonstrated high effectiveness in preventing malicious scaling out requests triggered by high-rate (Hulk) and low-rate (Slowloris) DDoS attacks. However, we noticed that in the case of Slowloris, the first scaling request may be authorized due to the attack's stealthiness. The asset is also integrated and tested in an extended scenario as part of UC5, demonstrating an end-to-end detection and mitigation of EDoS attack and the associated application-layer DDoS

attack. The scenario begins with the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator detecting malicious scaling requests, in which case it submits an anomaly report to AID via Kafka bus. The AID consumes this report and generates a security policy, which is enforced by the SO to trigger OULU's R12 asset (i.e., Privacy-Preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector) to perform network traffic anomaly detection in order to identify and block the source of the attack at the User Plane Function (UPF) level. More details on this end-to-end integration scenario and the obtained performance results will be reported in D5.3.

5.2.4. Updates related to the first prototype

The first prototype of the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator focused on setting up the testbed and developing the monitoring system for training dataset generation, as well as training and testing the DL model. The second phase focuses on integrating the asset with K8s's HPA and RIGOROUS framework's components to enable closed-loop attack mitigation. To this end, the following updates have been made:

- Update the EDoS's Monitoring System to use Service Mesh Istio instead of NGINX-to-Prometheus log file exporter to collect the performance metrics of the vCDN's Cloud-Native Network Functions (CNFs). The EDoS Monitoring System is now capable of collecting the resource usage and performance metrics at the service level using cAdvisor and Istio Envoy, respectively.
- Implementation of interfaces of the asset's components to enable their integration with K8s's HPA, as detailed in Section 5.2.1.
- Definition of a new data model for anomaly report in STIXv2 format, as detailed in Section 5.2.2, with integrated Kafka support for report publication.
- Creation of Docker images and manifest YAML files to enable automated deployment of the asset's components as services in a cloud-native platform. Beyond its local deployment in OULU's testbed, the created images and manifests have also served to demonstrate the asset's onboarding and deployment in UC5 through MIRO platform (<https://miro.onesource.pt/en>); a multi-domain resource orchestration platform that emerged from a collaborative research initiative between ONE and ICT-FI as part of the CHARITY project.

5.3. Security Testing - Digital Twin (DT)

The Digital Twin (DT) component developed within WP4 plays a critical role in enabling proactive and controlled cybersecurity testing. Rather than serving as a passive replica of the infrastructure, the DT in RIGOUROUS is designed as a security testing tool. It emulates realistic network behaviour and generates synthetic network traffic, including various cyberattack scenarios, to evaluate the response capabilities of other WP4 components, particularly DASC. Through its integration into the RIGOUROUS workflow, the DT supports the validation of interoperability, service resilience, and response logic under controlled threat conditions. This enables early identification of vulnerabilities stemming from protocol mismatches, policy misalignment, or configuration errors before these issues manifest in the operational network.

5.3.1. Component Architecture

The DT component in RIGOUROUS serves as a simulation and validation engine to proactively evaluate interoperability, misconfigurations, or potential policy violations across the cyber-physical energy infrastructure. It does not detect threats directly but emulates system behaviour under controlled configurations and test cases. Architecturally, the DT consists of:

- Perception layer which consists of RESs (their function is to send XML messages containing data readings to the gateway) , and gateways (their function is to receive XML messages from the smart meter and expects a specific format, including predefined fields and values)
- A simulation core that replicates the operational behaviour of RES units, gateways, control protocols, and network states ensuring a comprehensive virtual reconstruction for validation and optimization.
- Input APIs to receive real-time topology, system metadata, and simulated traffic profiles.
- Integration interfaces with the DASC engine to trigger remediation workflows when inconsistencies are identified. DASC supports document parsing, error classification, and service retrieval.

The DT runs independently or in coordination with live data, operating in a sandbox environment to avoid interference with actual control systems.

A schema of the description above can be seen in Figure 23:

Figure 23 DT component architecture

5.3.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The DT ingests pre-defined configuration files, policy rules, and simulated traffic profiles reflecting realistic control flows in the RES ecosystem. Data inputs include monitoring and logging of the following:

- Simulated packet flows (source, destination, size, protocol anomaly label)
- RES control parameters (e.g., SETPOINT_BINOUT, WINDC_ON, WINCSUSP)
- Gateway protocol characteristics (e.g., MQTT, REST, proprietary)
- Component responses (e.g., whether firewall rules were applied or variables updated)

This information is serialized in structured JSON or STIX-like format and transmitted to the DASC and optionally to the TRA/AID pipeline for additional assessment. The DT also includes an internal data repository for archiving past simulation runs and benchmarking the evolution of the system's resilience. A payload example is depicted in Table 19.

A Python script implements a lightweight MQTT-based “digital twin” for a photovoltaic (PV) resource: it connects to a designated broker, subscribes to a control command topic to receive real-time setpoint updates (including enable/suspend flags), and then continuously publishes a simulated production state message at 1 Hz. Each outgoing telemetry payload contains a UTC timestamp, device identifiers, the last valid setpoint (subject to control flags), a $\pm 5\%$ randomized jitter value to mimic measurement noise, and the raw command flags, all encoded in JSON. By decoupling command intake from state output in a background thread, the module enables reliable testing of downstream data consumers—dashboards, historians, or grid stability controllers—without requiring physical hardware.

Table 19 DT payload example

Field	Description
Payload example	<pre>{"HIST_TIMESTAMP": "2025-06-16T07:37:20.294935+00:00", "DEVICE_B1_NAME": "Ag.Christ", "DEVICE_B2_NAME": "FB1", "DEVICE_B3_NAME": "GFC1", "RES_TYPE": "PV", "LR_LFCMX": 16, "SETPOINT_BINOUT": 100, "GROSS_VALUE": 95.152, "WINDC_ON": 1, "WINCSUSP": 0}</pre>

When a mismatch is detected from the DASC, it proposes repairing mechanisms (e.g. reconfiguration to adapt affected components, modifying service parameters, updating protocol translations) in the corresponding components. These repairing actions are sent as mitigation plan to the RM to enforce the mitigation. Then, the Response-Mitigation Service of the RM component applies the mitigation action on the system by contacting its associated security agents and managers (Figure 24).

Figure 24 DT sequence diagram

5.3.3. Final Results

During the last period, the DT was successfully deployed in the WINGS testbed to generate traffic scenarios mimicking security threats. Figures 25 and 26 below present actual screenshots from the operational GUI of the DT component.

Figure 25 displays the live monitoring panel of the Digital Twin. The upper part shows the values of critical control variables for RES such as:

- SETPOINT_BINOUT: the curtailment limit for the RES unit,
- GROSS_VALUE: the actual measured energy production,
- WINDC_ON and WINCSUSP: operational control flags for enabling or suspending RES operation.

Operators can manually adjust these variables or let the DT simulate automated changes to emulate realistic system behaviour. On the right-hand panel, threat scenario buttons (e.g., DDoS, FDI) are made available for immediate simulation activation.

The lower section presents a live stream of "Message Events", which are time-stamped JSON messages generated and processed by the DT. Each message encapsulates control and telemetry data, source/destination information, and operational status. These messages are also forwarded to other RIGOROUS components (via Kafka) for further anomaly detection and mitigation handling. This setup verifies the Digital Twin's ability to produce realistic traffic and system signals under both normal and abnormal conditions.

Figure 25 DT GUI showing RES variables and message logging

Figures 26 illustrates the Digital Twin's security testing mode. The user interface now highlights two additional log sections: "Network Events" and "Policy Events".

- In the **Network Events** section, the DT records simulated traffic flows involving different network entities (e.g., RES, RES_CUT, gateways), along with flags for anomalous behaviours (such as unexpected command sequences or high-rate message bursts). These events are annotated using STIX-like formatting, including fields like anomaly_metric, source_ip, and flow_id, mimicking the outputs produced.
- The **Policy Events** section shows a timeline of security actions taken by the system in response to simulated threats. For example, in a FDI scenario, the system reacts by issuing a policy to suspend the RES (e.g., WINCSUSP = 1) or by deploying a firewall rule (action: drop) targeting malicious IPs. These actions are initially generated by the AID engine and dispatched via the Security Orchestrator.

Overall, this figure illustrates the closed-loop capability of the Digital Twin: not only does it simulate security threats, but it also tests the entire detection–decision–mitigation pipeline, including feedback validation and reconfiguration via DASC if a policy fails to enforce correctly.

Figure 26 DT interface simulating security attacks and displaying corresponding mitigation policy events

The DT consistently triggered fault cascades, and correctly activated DASC repairs when interoperability mismatches were present. This validates its capability to simulate complex attack chains and support end-to-end testing under realistic timing conditions.

5.3.4. Updates related to the first prototype

The final version of the DT has been upgraded to produce network traffic flow that simulates different type of attacks. It dynamically configures scenario parameters, generates threats for security testing and expands integration with DASC component. Compared to the initial prototype described in D4.2 [2], the DT now supports multi-node simulations and it emulates traffic flow of a RES. JSON-based configuration profiles were introduced, replacing hardcoded system topologies. Integration with DASC was formalized using Kafka messaging, enabling real-time triggering of composition or repair actions based on simulated inconsistencies. These updates improved both coverage and responsiveness, making the DT a reliable component in both validation and security planning.

5.4. Dynamic and Automated Service Composition - DASC

DASC plays a pivotal role in detecting and resolving interoperability issues and enforcing reactive or proactive mitigation strategies in scenarios where system components must dynamically adapt to security events, configuration mismatches, or policy enforcement failures. Its operation is especially critical in environments composed of heterogeneous IoT, edge, and cloud elements.

5.4.1. Component Architecture

The DASC is designed to ensure operational continuity in the presence of interoperability failures between components of the cyber-physical system. It plays a critical role in enabling resilience by dynamically detecting and resolving runtime incompatibilities across services. It is designed as a modular and event-driven service that interfaces with anomaly detection systems, security orchestrators, and the DT environment. The component consists of the following submodules (Figure 27):

- Parsing, Detection, and Classification Tool: This component is responsible for receiving alerts or triggers and then scans the files involved. It detects any mismatches or errors within these files and classifies or identifies the type of problem encountered. Essentially, it analyses the input data to classify the issue.

- Interoperability engine: Analyses service composition workflows and detects protocol mismatches between system components.
- Service Search, Composition, Problem Resolution: Once the issue is classified, this component kicks in. It searches available repositories or databases to find the corresponding services required to resolve the identified problem. If multiple issues are detected, it may call upon multiple services to compose a solution, ensuring that the problem is fully resolved.

Figure 27 DASC component architecture

5.4.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The data monitoring and data services for the DASC are depicted in the next workflow in Figure 28. The implementation of the DASC is tailored for policy translation. It involves monitoring translations from XML (Policies) to JSON (Drivers) formats.

The DT emulates RES data sources (topology files, system metadata, gateway/RES control parameters) and network traffic to simulate control flows and evaluate system compatibility. The format is translated into JSON/XML based simulation reports or anomaly flags (e.g. unsupported protocol detected, command not acknowledged). DT identifies a configuration inconsistency (e.g. a new gateway introduced using a different protocol stack) and publishes the traffic to the DASC. DASC detects and validates the protocol mismatches, investigates repair actions and determines how to reconfigure system interfaces or services and prepares a mitigation plan. The data services involved in the exchange are:

- Configuration ingestion service: Collects system state, and RES configuration status, parameters, etc.

- Simulation engine: DT emulates behaviour of the network and devices based on ingested configuration.
- Interoperability checker: Compares expected control flow and interface compatibility rules.
- Remediation orchestration: Receives problem context and applies automated service composition logic.

Figure 28 DASC sequence diagram

5.4.3. Final Results

The latest developments in DASC backend lead to extend the capabilities of the component. DASC is able to:

- Detect missing enforcement (e.g. firewall rule not applied).
- Retrieve configuration mismatches between points in the workflow (e.g. missing protocol adapter between RES gateway and RES_CUT).
- Successful logging of all actions.
- Apply a recomposition plan that restored enforcement compatibility.

As an example, we provide a combined execution of DT and DASC. The system simulates the reception and validation of JSON payloads transmitted by a Digital Twin system. It checks whether incoming data packets conform to an expected structure and ensures compatibility with downstream systems. This capability is crucial in scenarios where automated security enforcement or system reconfiguration relies on precise, schema-compliant input data. The tool serves both diagnostic and auto-healing roles in the interoperability workflow.

The DASC validation module operates as follows:

- **Payload Reception & Logging:** Each JSON payload arriving from the DT is captured and recorded in a structured log, including timestamp and source reference.
- **Schema Validation:** The system parses each payload and verifies whether all **expected fields**—based on a predefined schema—are present.
- **Content Visualization:** Payload content is displayed in a structured and human-readable format for traceability and debugging.
- **Missing Field Detection:** Any **omitted keys or fields** are explicitly logged, helping pinpoint the source of incomplete or outdated message structures.

- **Auto-repair Mechanism:** If missing fields are detected, the system dynamically **repairs the payload** by inserting a **placeholder diagnostic value** (e.g., -1) for each missing field. This approach maintains schema consistency without discarding potentially useful partial data.
- **Validation Confirmation:** Once the payload structure is complete—either as-is or post-repair—the system marks it as **ready for further processing**, triggering downstream actions such as DASC-driven reconfiguration or policy regeneration.

In the first test case scenario (Figure 29), the incoming JSON payload was complete and conformed fully to the expected schema. The system:

- Logged the event as successful,
- Displayed all fields accurately,
- Determined no repair actions were necessary.

The payload was marked as valid and fully compatible with downstream components, enabling it to be routed directly into the reconfiguration pipeline if required.

```
[INFO] --- Running with VALID payload ---
[INFO] Traffic detected...
[INFO] Actual Payload:
[INFO]
{
  "HIST_TIMESTAMP": "2025-06-16T07:37:20.294935+00:00",
  "DEVICE_B1_NAME": "Ag.Christ",
  "DEVICE_B2_NAME": "FB1",
  "DEVICE_B3_NAME": "GFC1",
  "RES_TYPE": "PV",
  "LR_LFCMX": 16,
  "SETPOINT_BINOUT": 100,
  "GROSS_VALUE": 95.152,
  "WINDC_ON": 1,
  "WINCSUSP": 0,
  "SCADA_SETPOINT_FB": 42
}
[INFO] Payload repair not required.
[INFO] Payload structure up to date.
```

Figure 29 Valid payload scenario

In the second test case scenario (Figure 30), the received payload was missing one or more required fields. The system:

- Identified the missing field(s),
- Logged the discrepancy,
- Injected a placeholder value (-1) in place of each missing entry,
- Labelled the repaired payload with a flag to alert downstream components that this data may require contextual handling.

This validation-repair cycle ensured continuity of service composition logic, preventing system crashes or misconfigurations due to malformed input.

```
[INFO] --- Running with OUTDATED payload ---
[INFO] Traffic detected..
[WARNING] Outdated payload detected..
[WARNING] Missing keys detected: ['SCADA_SETPOINT_FB']
[INFO] Repairing payload structure
[INFO] Repaired Payload:
[INFO]
{
  "HIST_TIMESTAMP": "2025-06-16T07:37:20.294935+00:00",
  "DEVICE_B1_NAME": "Ag.Christ",
  "DEVICE_B2_NAME": "FB1",
  "DEVICE_B3_NAME": "GFC1",
  "RES_TYPE": "PV",
  "LR_LFCMX": 16,
  "SETPOINT_BINOUT": 100,
  "GROSS_VALUE": 95.152,
  "WINDC_ON": 1,
  "WINCSUSP": 0,
  "SCADA_SETPOINT_FB": -1
}
[INFO] Payload structure up to date.
```

Figure 30 Outdated payload example

These tests demonstrate the robustness and resilience of the DASC validation module. Its ability to accept partial input, repair it on the fly, and transparently log actions ensures seamless integration even under conditions of inconsistent or degraded input quality. This functionality is especially important when systems such as the Digital Twin simulate non-standard conditions or legacy message formats.

5.4.4. Updates related to the first prototype

Compared to the first prototype described in D4.2 [2], the final version of the DASC includes the following enhancements:

- Improved repair logic based on lessons learned during refined UC3 scenarios. DASC now supports conditional reconfigurations based on attack type and source.
- Able to detect a vast amount of mismatches such as Protocol Mismatches and Vulnerabilities which can introduce security loopholes, incompatible data formats that can lead to improper data handling, allowing attackers to manipulate or inject malicious data, and security policy enforcement across diverse systems.
- Digital twin integration to enable proactive validation of configurations before field deployment.
- Kafka messaging support.
- Enhanced protocol adaptation engine through support for JSON/XML mapping and protocol version negotiation between components.

5.5. Slicing Mitigation Planner Service

The Slicing Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS) is a component developed by UWS within the RIGOUROUS project to plan mitigation actions against cyber threats in 5G networks. Based on

alerts raised by the Network Security Flow Monitoring (NSFM) component, the SMPS defines mitigation policies and selects the appropriate enforcement points in the data plane. Actions may include dropping, redirecting, or mirroring traffic, or enforcing a network slice. Enforcement locations follow predefined rules such as "near the source" or "along the end-to-end (E2E) path." These strategies can be automated using a policy engine, allowing administrators to define tailored responses to different attack types.

5.5.1. Component Architecture

The SMPS workflow, illustrated in Figure 31, begins when the NSFM component detects a malicious 5G flow and publishes an alert to the NSFM Events exchange. Upon receiving this event, the Planner subcomponent of the SMPS is triggered. Its main function is to generate a mitigation plan with the necessary information to stop the ongoing cyberattack. Using a prescriptive analytics approach, the Planner answers four key questions. First, what action should be taken: in the RIGOROUS context, the selected action is the enforcement of a network slice, including technical details such as whether to use Traffic Control, OpenvSwitch (OVS), or Iptables. This information is packaged into a structured object containing all parameters needed for enforcement. Second, when the action should occur for the current use case, the mitigation is immediate, though other scenarios could involve scheduled or rate-based actions. Third, how long the mitigation should last: in this case, the Planner determines that rules should remain active indefinitely. Finally, where the action should be enforced: the SMPS identifies the full E2E path of the malicious flow and selects appropriate mitigation points, typically closer to the source, but adaptable depending on the attack context. This structured process allows SMPS to support real-time, targeted response planning across complex 5G/6G network infrastructures.

Figure 31 Sequence diagram of SMPS architecture

5.5.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The SMPS relies on detailed network flow information provided by the NSFM component. To compute the E2E path of a detected flow across the B5G infrastructure, the SMPS correlates data from both the flow and topology domains. The required flow information includes source and destination IP addresses, ports, transport protocols, and other relevant packet-level attributes. This is complemented by topological data such as identified interfaces, network devices, and host locations. Additional context is obtained from the Topology Inventory Agent (TIA) component, as shown in Figure 31, which enriches the path analysis with up-to-date infrastructure mappings. By combining these datasets, the SMPS can accurately model the complete network trajectory of suspicious or degraded flows. This enables the application of prescriptive analytics to evaluate possible mitigation actions and generate informed, targeted Mitigation Plans. These plans are then used to guide automated responses within the self-protection loop, ensuring that corrective measures are both efficient and topologically aware, enhancing the resilience and security of network slice operations in the B5G environment.

5.5.3. Final Results

The following results are obtained from the experiments and testbed scenarios depicted in Section 6.2 of this same deliverable.

Figure 32 illustrates the number of mitigation plans generated by the SMPS component across different experimental scenarios. Each plan typically consists of two decisions: the creation of a new network slice with defined parameters and the redirection of the identified malicious flow to that slice. These actions are fundamental to enabling automated and dynamic responses to detected threats.

For all configurations, the SMPS consistently generates approximately six plans per infected UE, aligning with the number of predefined mitigation points per attacker. This consistency is visible across the smaller-scale scenarios, where both detection accuracy and topological awareness remain high. As the network scales, however, the number of generated plans begins to decrease in the largest experiments, particularly for 64 and 128 UEs in the 2 and 4 Edge configurations.

This decline suggests that while the SMPS planning logic remains consistent, its effectiveness becomes constrained under high-complexity conditions. The probable causes are the increased strain on system resources, delays in receiving complete topological or flow data, or possible loss of information due to overload. As a result, the SMPS might miss opportunities to generate plans for certain detected attacks, highlighting a scalability challenge for future iterations of the mitigation planning process.

Figure 32 Number of mitigation plans generated by the SMPS

Figure 33 presents the average number of E2E mitigation points calculated by the SMPS across varying topological scenarios. These mitigation points correspond to virtual interfaces within OVS bridges, strategically selected along the network path to enforce mitigation actions. Their location and number are dynamically determined based on the deployment topology, specifically how Edge and Core servers connect to their tenants. The expected total number of mitigation points for complete coverage in each scenario is 6 for 1 Edge, 8 for 2 Edges, and 12 for 4 Edges.

Results confirm that the SMPS performs optimally for low to moderate loads, consistently identifying all expected mitigation points from 8 to 32 UEs. This indicates that the component maintains full topological awareness and successfully infers the best enforcement locations under manageable complexity. However, as the scale increases to 64 and 128 UEs in the 4 Edge configuration, a reduction in identified mitigation points is observed.

This decrease suggests a degradation in the system's capacity to fully process topological and flow data under high-load conditions. The complexity of the expanded topology likely impacts the timely availability of network information, reducing the effectiveness of the planning module. Despite this limitation, the system still identifies a substantial number of mitigation points, maintaining a robust response capacity even under stress, which validates the approach applicability to large-scale, dynamic 5G/6G networks.

Figure 33 Average number of E2E mitigation points calculated by the SMPS

5.5.4. Updates related to the first prototype

The first prototype of the SMPS offered basic capabilities for E2E path computation, relying on static topology data and limited flow information, with minimal integration into the broader self-protection architecture. It was primarily a proof of concept, focused on validating the feasibility of correlating network paths with known threats. In contrast, the final prototype features full integration with the NSFM and the TIA, enabling real-time correlation of flow-level data with dynamic topological information, as shown in results in Figure 32 and Figure 33. This allows the SMPS to compute accurate and up-to-date E2E paths in complex B5G scenarios and to generate prescriptive, context-aware Mitigation Plans. The final version thus supports automated, closed-loop mitigation actions, significantly enhancing its responsiveness, scalability, and operational relevance within the Network Service Provider (NSP) framework.

6 SOAR DRIVEN NETWORK FLOW AND TOPOLOGY MONITORING

6.1. Introduction

This section presents UWS and Aston' contributions to the RIGOUROUS framework within WP4, focusing on the reactive control loop and monitoring of network flow and topology. The implemented closed control loop continuously observes the network and uses feedback to adjust performance and security, following principles similar to SOAR systems. It acts as the sensing layer, monitoring different network domains, while analysis is handled by dedicated components. This modular approach improves scalability and efficiency; for example, an IDS can generate alerts based on monitored data, specifying the type of threat and affected resources.

6.2. Testbed

The following section describes the testbed used to execute a set of experiments, whose results are presented and analysed in the sections dedicated to each UWS/ASTON component. The WP4 components tested within the scope of this testbed and its scenarios include the NSFM, TIA, and SMPS. Each results section for these components will refer back to this testbed description.

The experiments are based on scenarios that emulate a 5G/6G network infrastructure with varying topology, including different numbers of connected UEs, Edge servers, and gNodeBs. These scenarios are emulated using the CORE network emulator, a tool that leverages Linux network namespaces (netns) to simulate containers and nodes representing network elements in the infrastructure. An extension developed by UWS/Aston automates the creation of these topologies, executes the experiments, and stores the results in a SQL database. All experiments were conducted on a physical server running Ubuntu 20.04 LTS with kernel version 5.15.0, equipped with a 56-core Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2660 v4 @ 2.00GHz and 128 GB DDR4 2400 MHz RAM.

The experiment involves a DDoS attack launched by a botnet of infected UEs targeting a victim located in a different domain of the 5G/6G infrastructure. Despite the separation of domains, all infected UEs route their traffic through the same network infrastructure defined in the scenario. The goal is to mitigate the attack using an E2E network slice per affected UE. Several components are involved in this process: the NSFM detects the malicious flows, the TIA provides topological information, the SMPS plans the mitigation strategy, the SO and SM orchestrate the mitigation actions, and the NSP enforces the corresponding policies in the data plane. The DDoS attack is a fixed-rate UDP flood, with each infected UE generating 10 Mbps of traffic. The mitigation uses network slices configured with an E2E bandwidth limit of 1 Kbps.

The topology of the 5G/6G scenarios varies as shown in Table 20. There are nine main configurations:

- With one Edge server, scenarios include 8, 16, and 32 connected UEs.
- With two Edge servers, scenarios include 16, 32, and 64 UEs.
- With four Edge servers, scenarios include 32, 64, and 128 UEs.

Table 20 Scenarios executed for experiments with SOAR loop, SMPS, SM and NSP components

Scenario name	No of Edge Servers	No of infected UEs	Total attack BW (Mbps)
A1	1	8	80
A2		16	160
A3		32	320
B1	2	16	160
B2		32	320
B3	4	32	320

C2		64	640
C3		128	1280

Figure 34 shows the topological view of the 5G/6G network infrastructure used in the experiments. From left to right, the diagram represents the main segments of the 5G network: device, 5G RAN, 5G Edge, transport, 5G Core, and inter-domain. Devices connect to antennas, each equipped with a Distributed Unit (DU) that converts Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI) traffic into standard Ethernet and IP. This traffic is then routed to the Edge server, where two Digital Service Providers (DSPs), A and B, encapsulate user traffic using the GTP protocol to support mobility. Before the traffic exits the Edge domain, it is encapsulated again using the VXLAN protocol to enable multi-tenancy and isolate the traffic of each DSP. In the Core domain, the traffic undergoes the reverse process: de-encapsulation of VXLAN and GTP, followed by routing to the destination servers on the internet. Red-labelled dots in the OVS switches mark the mitigation points where the NSP enforces mitigation policies, effectively creating the End-to-End network slice.

Figure 34 Logical representation of the 5G/6G network infrastructure of the scenarios deployed within the experiments for NSFM, TIA, SMPS, SM and NSP components

6.3. Network Security Flow Monitoring - NSFM

This subsection presents a first functional prototype of the NSFM RIGOROUS asset as part of the UWS and Aston contribution to WP4. A description of the component architecture is provided along with the results gathered in the testbed deployed in UWS premises.

6.3.1. Component Architecture

Figure 35 presents the architecture of the NSFM component, which builds on existing Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS) tools such as Snort by adding support for detailed metadata extraction and classification of 5G network packets. These enhancements allow the control loop to apply mitigation policies to specific malicious flows, avoiding unnecessary disruptions to the broader network infrastructure. The architecture includes two main subcomponents. The first is a Snort-based NIDS, configured to detect DDoS attacks using predefined rules. It monitors mirrored traffic from the 5G Core segment at the Service Layer, ensuring no impact on the production data

plane. When a suspicious flow is detected, Snort generates an alert and logs it in binary format using the Unified2 protocol. The second subcomponent, NextGen NIDS, reads these alerts, extracts full packet data using libpcap, and performs in-depth classification. It supports various encapsulation layers, such as GTP for LTE flows and VXLAN, GENEVE, or GRE for tenant isolation in 5G networks. The result is a structured JSON object containing both classification results and alert metadata, which is then forwarded to the rest of the system for further processing.

UWS Network Security Flow Monitoring

Figure 35 Sequence diagram of the UWS NSFM architecture

6.3.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The data monitoring and data services layer in the system is composed of two key components: the NSFM and the TIA. The NSFM is responsible for capturing and recording metadata related to 5G/6G network flows. This includes information such as source and destination IP addresses, ports, transport protocols, timestamps, and flow duration. These flow-level details are essential for detecting anomalies, identifying potentially compromised flows, and enabling correlation with topological context for accurate threat localization and mitigation.

6.3.3. Final Results

Figure 36 presents the number of detected DDoS attacks by the NSFM module across varying numbers of infected UEs (x-axis), under three different edge configurations: 1, 2, and 4 Edge nodes (left to right). This analysis helps evaluate how the detection capability scales as both the number of infected devices and the distribution across Edge nodes increase.

Under the 1 Edge configuration, the detection rate remains consistent and high. The system detects 8, 15.7, and 26 attacks out of 8, 16, and 32 infected UEs, respectively, reflecting a nearly linear response and no notable degradation. In contrast, the 2 Edge configuration shows a slight decrease in detection accuracy, particularly for larger attack scenarios. While detection remains

high for 16 UEs (15/16), performance decreases for 32 (27/32) and 64 (31/64) infected devices. This reduction is likely due to the increased complexity introduced by distributing the network across multiple Edges, which can affect the propagation of attack signatures and increase detection latency.

When scaling to 4 Edges, the system demonstrates more stable detection at moderate loads, achieving 26.3 detections for 32 UEs, a similar value as for 2 Edges with 64 UEs (32/64). However, a notable drop appears at 128 UEs, with 32.3 attacks detected, highlighting the impact of scaling limits. This degradation results from the combined stress of managing a large-scale emulated topology and the overhead of handling coordinated attacks across distributed Edge environments. These results suggest that while the detection system performs reliably under moderate scaling, optimizations are needed to maintain accuracy under large, distributed attack scenarios.

Figure 36 Number of detected DDoS attack by the NSFM for multiple UEs and Edge server configurations

Figure 37 illustrates the average time required by the NSFM module to detect and report a single alert, across increasing numbers of infected UEs and under 1, 2, and 4 Edge configurations. This metric is crucial for assessing the responsiveness of the detection mechanism under varying network sizes and levels of distribution.

In the 1 Edge configuration, the average time per alert increases from 3.6 seconds with 8 infected UEs to 12.6 seconds with 32. Although this may initially appear as a linear increase, the number of UEs is scaled in powers of two. Therefore, the relative growth in detection time is moderate and suggests that the NSFM can scale reasonably well under a centralized set-up.

For the 2 Edge configuration, a similar trend is observed, with times of 7.0, 13.1, and 15.2 seconds for 16, 32, and 64 UEs, respectively. The rate of increase begins to flatten, indicating that distributing the load over more Edge nodes might help mitigate detection time growth, even as the network size increases. This effect is more evident in the 4 Edge set-up, where detection time rises only slightly between 32, 64, and 128 UEs, 12.8, 15.6, and 15.8 seconds, respectively, showing a clear stabilization. This behaviour highlights the potential benefits of scaling out the detection infrastructure, as additional Edge resources can absorb the increased computational and networking load without significantly affecting per-alert detection latency.

Figure 37 Total time consumed to report a single DDoS attacks by the NSFM for multiple UEs and Edge Servers

Figure 38 shows the average total time consumed by the NSFM module to detect and report all attack events for each experiment. The results are segmented by Edge configuration (1, 2, and 4 Edges) and plotted against an increasing number of infected UEs. This metric complements the per-alert time by providing a broader view of system scalability and cumulative detection effort.

In the 1 Edge configuration, total detection time grows from 7.1 seconds at 8 UEs to 25.1 seconds at 32 UEs. This increase follows the same general trend as observed in the per-alert time, with the system requiring proportionally more time as the number of threats increases. However, the progression remains manageable and suggests that a centralized configuration handles moderate-scale attacks efficiently.

For the 2 Edge set-up, the total detection time also scales predictably: 14.1, 26.1, and 30.3 seconds for 16, 32, and 64 infected UEs, respectively. Although the absolute values are higher than the single-Edge case, the rate of increase diminishes with scale, indicating some amortization of detection overhead across distributed resources.

Finally, under the 4 Edge configuration, the time consumed rises more gradually despite a substantial increase in infected UEs. From 25.5 seconds at 32 UEs to 31.7 seconds at 128 UEs.

Figure 38 Total time consumed to report all DDoS attacks by the NSFM for multiple UEs and Edge Servers

The three figures analysing NSFM performance demonstrate that the detection system maintains a high level of efficiency and responsiveness under varying scales and Edge configurations. Although the NSFM remains centralized, increasing the number of Edge nodes, used to spread the network topology and introduce additional attack vectors, does affect detection dynamics. The number of detected attacks remains consistently high for moderate numbers of infected UEs, with some degradation observed at larger scales due to the increased complexity of the emulated environment. Both the average and total detection times grow with the number of UEs, but this

growth tends to stabilize as the topology scales. These results indicate that the centralized NSFM system remains effective even as the network expands and becomes more distributed in terms of topology.

6.3.4. Updates related to the first prototype

The first prototype of the NSFM provided basic functionality for monitoring 5G/6G network flows, primarily limited to collecting static or periodically exported flow records. It lacked support for real-time analysis and had minimal integration with other components in the system. In its final version, however, the NSFM has been significantly enhanced to support real-time ingestion of flow metadata. This upgrade enables dynamic threat detection and immediate correlation with mitigation workflows, making the component far more responsive and operationally effective within the self-protection framework.

6.4. Topology Inventory Agent - TIA

This subsection presents the final prototype and results of the TIA RIGUROUS asset as part of the UWS and Aston contribution to WP4. A description of the component architecture is provided, along with preliminary results gathered from the testbed deployed in UWS premises.

6.4.1. Component Architecture

The TIA is a distributed software component in the RIGUROUS framework responsible for discovering and maintaining up-to-date network topology information across the RAN, MEC, Transport, and Core segments. It identifies physical and virtual interfaces, switches, routers, and other network devices, and provides this information to the SM and SMPS to support network slice deployment during cyber-attack mitigation. TIA instances are deployed across all data plane segments to ensure comprehensive visibility. Its architecture includes three subcomponents: the Topology Collector, which periodically gathers local network data using Linux tools; the Topology Database, which stores and updates the aggregated information from all collectors; and the Topology Sender, which notifies other components of topology changes via RabbitMQ messages. Figure 39 illustrates a TIA deployment, showing agents distributed across physical hosts and a centralized database in a control node.

Figure 39 Distributed deployment of TIA component

6.4.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The TIA continuously collects and updates topological information about the 5G infrastructure. This includes attributes such as the interface name (e.g., eth3, br-ctf-n20), interface type (e.g., physical, logical, Linux bridge, OVS), the hostname of the device where the interface is detected, MAC and IPv4 addresses (if configured), netmask, configured transmission speed, MTU, operational state (UP or DOWN), and whether the interface operates in promiscuous mode. This topological data provides critical context for network visibility and supports higher-level analytics, such as E2E path computation and mitigation planning, within the self-protection framework.

6.4.3. Final Results

The following results are obtained from the experiments and testbed scenarios depicted in Section 6.2 of this same deliverable.

Figure 40 shows the total number of topological elements detected and reported by the TIA in each experiment. These elements include network infrastructure components such as hosts, links, switches, routers, and interfaces. Understanding the full topological view is fundamental for the SMPS to evaluate network paths and make informed mitigation decisions. As before, results are grouped by Edge configuration: 1, 2, and 4 Edges.

In the 1 Edge configuration, the number of detected topological devices scales moderately with the number of UEs: from 341 devices at 8 UEs, to 381 at 16 UEs, and 461 at 32 UEs. This trend reflects a direct relationship between the number of participating endpoints and the resulting network complexity in a single-domain deployment.

When extending the topology across 2 Edges, the number of devices increases significantly even for the same number of UEs. For instance, 16 UEs in 2 Edges yield 538 devices, compared to 381 in 1 Edge, an increase of 157 elements. The count grows further to 618 and 778 for 32 and 64 UEs respectively, indicating how the distributed deployment increases the number of interconnection points, links, and routing components required to support cross-Edge communication.

With 4 Edges, the growth becomes even more pronounced. At 32 UEs, the system reports 944 topological devices, 483 more than in the equivalent 1 Edge setup. The number climbs to 1104 at 64 UEs and 1422.3 at 128 UEs. This considerable increase highlights the importance of maintaining a comprehensive and up-to-date global view of the network topology. Without this information,

the SMPS would lack the context necessary to deploy effective, topology-aware mitigation strategies in large-scale, multi-domain environments.

Figure 40 Number of detected and reported devices, connections, and interfaces by the TIA for multiple UEs and Edge server configurations

6.4.4. Updates related to the first prototype

The TIA, in its initial implementation, functioned as a static topology snapshot tool, capturing only a limited set of interface attributes without support for continuous updates or real-time state tracking. This limited its utility in dynamic network environments. The final prototype of the TIA introduced substantial improvements, evolving into a fully dynamic inventory system capable of continuously discovering and updating comprehensive interface information, including operational state, MTU, configured speed, and promiscuous mode status. These enhancements greatly improved the accuracy and timeliness of topological insights, positioning the TIA as a critical enabler of automated and context-aware mitigation strategies.

7 ROBUST AND PRIVACY PRESERVING AI

7.1. Introduction

The increasing complexity and interconnectedness of cyber-physical systems in B5G/6G environments have introduced new challenges for secure, resilient, and privacy-preserving operations. In response, the RIGUROUS project—through WP4 has developed AI-driven components aimed at enhancing anomaly detection, privacy protection, decision-making, and mitigation. The overarching objective of WP4 is to enable adaptive and intelligent cybersecurity mechanisms that operate across different layers of modern network infrastructures while preserving data confidentiality and ensuring interoperability. To achieve this, various partners have contributed modular, yet interoperable assets. ICT-FI developed the EaaS component, which offers scalable, cloud-fog-based cryptographic operations through RESTful APIs, enabling secure data handling and integration with FL modules. The solution leverages Kubernetes for dynamic orchestration, monitoring, and real-time responsiveness. OULU contributed with a Moving Target Defense-based Federated Learning (MTD-FL) framework that enhances model robustness by dynamically excluding potentially compromised participants based on traffic analysis and reinforcement learning. This mechanism significantly improves resilience against model poisoning attacks. Meanwhile, UMU led the development of the Privacy-Preserving Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) sharing module, which utilizes privacy-enhancing technologies like k-anonymity and k-map to anonymize sensitive data such as IDS logs before their exchange via MISP platforms. These assets form a cohesive framework that addresses critical cybersecurity needs in emerging intelligent systems. Each component supports real-world deployment and has been validated in testbeds across various use cases. The architecture ensures modularity, interoperability, and adaptability for integration in WP5.

7.2. MTD based Robust AI

The MTD concept reduces cyber-threats by dynamically adjusting network properties to distort adversary knowledge to trigger the attack. In the first phase of our results, we proposed a multi-model based FL for Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) environment. It incorporates multiple models in the training of the main model, to distort adversary knowledge and operate as an MTD strategy. Through in-lab testing we found this strategy does not work when the attacker achieves a full control over the training process in the compromised devices. To overcome this issue, we have introduced a novel MTD-FL which empowers FL with a dynamic selection of participants in the learning, as an MTD strategy to distort the assumption of participation of all devices in FL. Based on device-level traffic analysis, a MTD strategy dynamically changes the participants to remove the devices that are potential to be targeted in the future. Sections below give more details over the architecture, data management, the results, and the integration progress.

Figure 41 MTD-FL scheme

7.2.1. Component Architecture

The MTD-FL scheme dynamically changes the participants in the learning as an MTD strategy, to make it harder for an attacker to maintain a foothold. The participation decision is performed in response to suspicious activities in learning iterations. Figure 41 shows the MTD-FL scheme. The histories of security events of the devices are logged. Considering that the attacker sends malicious control traffic to devices to compromise them to perform malicious tasks e.g., updating poisoned models, traffic analysis can be a clue in the prediction of the attack occurrence at devices in the future. A Recurrent Neural Network (RNN)-based scheme is employed to predict the poisoning attack threats in the devices. The traffic features are given as input to an RNN and the output neuron predicts the attack occurrence.

Based on the predicted values of RNN and the state of the network in terms of available computation resources and wireless status of MEC, the state of the system is determined. Accordingly, a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) based scheme is employed for MTD strategy, based on which the participants in the next iteration are specified. We used the DRL method in [16]. While the action of the DRL, defines the participants, the reward is calculated as aggregation of time and accuracy, to ensure the FL performance.

7.2.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

These categories of data have been utilised for validation:

- **Wireless communication:** For the wireless communication, the settings, including the transmission bandwidth, and transmission power, have been configured according to the 6G settings outlined in the literature (e.g., [17], [18]).
- **Computation:** The computation capabilities have been set according to the MEC capabilities in the literature (e.g., [17]).
- **DDoS data:** We used CICDDoS 2019 data set [19], comprising realistic traffic to abstract the communications for legitimate and DDoS attack traffic through protocols e.g., HTTP, FTP. We have randomly distributed instances composed of UDPLag and SYN DDoS attacks, among devices for training, as well as for the purpose of testing. The dataset provides 87 IP

flow features e.g., source/destination IP addresses/ports, protocols, flow packet statistics, flag-related information, etc., which we utilise for the attack detection.

- **Malicious Traffic at Devices:** We used the Botnet attack trace in [21] to generate the malicious traffic at devices. It provides capabilities for the attacker to attack devices and upload/download. The data set has recorded the legitimate and attack traffic features (total of 78 features) e.g., traffic duration, total packets, packet/flow/header/segment statistics, etc.

The services offered by MTD-based FL with capabilities of training a master model with a set of slave models, as an MTD strategy to deceive the attacker and improve the accuracy of recognition, has been implemented in OULU test bed, an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Platinum 8358 CPU with 2.6 GHz frequency and 64 GB RAM, and using Python and Flask. It exposes the POST and GET endpoints as below:

POST: / LAB_MTDaaS—It defines the parameters that are involved in FL and MTD strategy.

GET: / LAB_MTDaaS—It demonstrates the results in terms of achieved accuracy and resilience against model poisoning attacks.

Note that the data for the training and testing data are fetched by calling external services through HTTP requests, which have been provided by ONE. Table 21 illustrates the schema of a GET request, when Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) with 32 hidden neurons and GRU with 28 hidden neurons are used as respectively master and slave models for a federation process with 6 clients, in 5 iterations.

Table 21 Request Schema for MTD-based FL

Field	Description
Request/Data Schema	{ "id": "string", "num_of_clients": "string", "num_of_master_model_neurons": "string", " num_of_slave_model_neurons ": "string", "num_of_itr": "string", "attack_scenario": "string"}
Request/Data Example	{ "id": "0", "num_of_clients": "6", "num_of_master_model_neurons": "32", " num_of_slave_model_neurons ": "28", "num_of_itr": "5", "attack_scenario": "0"}

Table 22 The results of Botnet attack anticipation

Model	Accuracy	FP	FN
GRU 5	0.87	0.06	0.92
GRU 8	0.77	0.24	0.27
GRU 11	0.51	0.49	0.37

Figure 42 The gained accuracy in DDoS attack detection.

Figure 43 The ratio of excluded malicious models in federated learning

7.2.3. Final Results

The MTD-based FL has been validated under model poisoning attack in [22]. There is a 4×4 grid environment with 100 m width for each grid cell, where 10 devices in random locations, collaborate in detecting DDoS attack. In the top-left and bottom-right corners, two BSs with coverage radius of 300 m, provide edge computing capabilities with CPU frequencies of 3.2 and 2.6 GHz, respectively. The transmission bandwidth of BSs is 28 and 30 MHz respectively. At each iteration, 10000 and 2500 instances of CICDDoS 2019 data set [19] are randomly distributed among devices for training and testing. GRU with hidden layer size of 8 neurons is used for the DDoS attacks detection.

At each iteration, the adversary targets up to 4 random devices and sends malicious traffic [21] to the compromised devices to take control and to update malicious models. We exploited 12000 and 30000 random sequences of benign/attack events in the Botnet trace, in the training and the test phases, respectively. Table 22 shows the obtained performance.

We evaluated GRU with 5, 8 and 11 hidden neurons. GRU 5 has achieved the highest accuracy of 87%. However, its False Negative (FN) is 92% which is high. GRU with 8 hidden neurons has gained accuracy of 77% and a lower FN of 0.27 and we used it for Botnet attack anticipation. MTD-FL performance is compared with these baselines:

- i) **FL** is the scenario of FL without attack.
- ii) **FL-With Attack** which is the scenario after poisoning attack.
- iii) **RND-MTD** where topology mutation happens by blocking 4 random participants at each iteration.

Figure 42 illustrates the accuracy of DDoS attack detection. Due to federation, the accuracy of attack detection increases to 92% in the fifth iteration. When there is no MTD strategy, the accuracy decreases to 15% in the first iteration. The side effect worsens in iterations, due to more injections of poisoned models. RND-MTD has a chance to exclude malicious devices and increases the accuracy up to 42%. MTD-FL raises the accuracy up to 88%. The reason is that it recognizes the potential of malicious models Figure 43 shows the ratio of excluded malicious models.

Generally, MTD-FL has outperformed RND-MTD and could exclude 92%-96% of malicious models in the aggregation phase. The reason is that in contrast with random exclusion strategy in RND-MTD, in MTD-FL the topology mutation is optimised based on anticipated status of devices (being Byzantine or benign), thereby omitting the Byzantine anticipated models. Finally, we found the

time of FL in MTD-FL in the range of 0.3 ms to 0.5 ms which is acceptable for ultra-low-latency applications.

7.2.4. Updates related to the first prototype

The multi-model FL with random selection of models, as an MTD mechanism has been initially integrated with an anomaly detection scenario in Use Case 6. The evaluation over the data has shown acceptable accuracy.

A final plan for a comprehensive integration has been designed. The final version of the integration according to the final plan is under development. In this direction, the neural network in deep reinforcement learning agent of the solution has been trained to decide about model selection in the MTD strategy. In future, as part of UC5, the learning agent will be integrated and the integration with final comprehensive features will be provided in the final deliverable of WP5.

7.3. Encryption-as-a-Service - EaaS

7.3.1. Component Architecture

The EaaS asset is deployed on the ICTFI Kubernetes testbed, hosted on cloud servers provided by OneSource. This testbed is designed to support multi-node Kubernetes environments, offering a platform for deploying scalable and distributed services. It leverages Kubernetes built-in controllers, such as Deployment and ReplicaSet, to ensure efficient load balancing, high availability, and fault tolerance. These features make the testbed an ideal environment for EaaS, where secure and scalable cryptographic operations are critical. One of the standout capabilities of the ICT-FI testbed is its theoretical support for up to 100 nodes, making it suitable for large-scale applications. However, practical limitations arise as the node count increases, introducing challenges in managing computational resources effectively. This limitation underscores the need for careful resource allocation and monitoring when deploying EaaS-services. Despite these constraints, the testbed provides a reliable environment for testing and validating cryptographic frameworks under real conditions [30,31]. The ICT-FI testbed also has secure and controlled access. Due to high CPU and processing, remote access is currently unavailable. This restriction minimizes potential security risks and ensures that the testbed's computational resources are fully dedicated to hosting and running the deployed services. While this limits the flexibility of external collaborators, it enhances the testbed's stability and performance for testing and validating EaaS assets.

Figure 44 The architecture used for deploying the EaaS framework on Kubernetes in ICTFI testbed [30,32]

The architecture enables the dynamic allocation of encryption and decryption instances across available nodes (Figure 44). This ensures minimal downtime and supports the scalability requirements of the EaaS framework. With its focus on supporting cryptographic operations, the testbed is well-aligned with the objectives of RIGOUROUS, with adaptable solutions. The EaaS framework Kubernetes multi-node capabilities for scalable deployment of encryption and decryption. Each service instance runs in separate pods, distributed across the cluster to optimize resource utilization. This architecture enhances reliability by isolating failures, which minimizes downtime (Figure 45).

The EaaS deployment model ensures scaling based on workload to support high availability and adaptability. This enables the system to dynamically add or remove instances and fluctuations in service usage without compromising performance. EaaS can handle diverse and dynamic cryptographic workloads, meeting the needs of various applications, from small-scale IoT devices to large-scale cloud services. EaaS will also be deployed as an application on the multi-domain intelligence resource orchestration (MIRO) system. The platform also emphasizes user customization through a web-based interface (Figure 46).

Figure 46 The EaaS user customization through a web-based interface from small-scale IoT devices

encryption and decryption

This interface allows clients to configure their encryption and decryption parameters according to their requirements. Users can select their preferred cryptographic algorithms, define instance configurations, and specify deployment locations (Figure 47 and Figure 48). Additionally, they can determine the duration of their encryption and decryption services, giving them complete control over their security setup [30,33].

Figure 47 The EaaS cryptographic for encryption deployment setup

Figure 48 The EaaS cryptographic for decryption deployment setup

EaaS integrates service meshes within the Kubernetes environment to enhance system performance and observability for the basic deployment setup. This layered architecture also separates frequently accessed components, such as encryption keys, to the fog layer, ensuring

low-latency access while relying on the cloud for resources [33]. The EaaS framework utilizes multiple interfaces to ensure seamless integration and secure communication with other assets. The asset uses HTTP and RESTful APIs, which are widely adopted for security and scalability in distributed systems (Figure 49).

The primary interaction occurs between the EaaS framework and the Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning (PPFL) anomaly detector, developed by Oulu. This interface facilitates the secure transmission of requests for encryption and decryption operations, enabling EaaS to process sensitive data in real-time. The setup is designed to ensure data privacy and confidentiality, in line with the principles of FL, where sensitive data remains local to its source.

Figure 49 HTTP post request and include the authorization token with the EaaS [30]

The REST APIs in the EaaS system are designed to support both synchronous and asynchronous communication, allowing participants to securely transmit requests and receive processed results. Each interaction includes several key parameters: participant identifiers, which uniquely identify the entities involved in the encryption or decryption process; the data payload, representing the information to be securely encrypted or decrypted; and the cryptographic algorithm, specifying the method to be applied, such as AES, RSA, or Paillier. These APIs ensure that every request is processed using the appropriate cryptographic technique, maintaining data confidentiality and guaranteeing that only authorized entities can access the final output. This mechanism preserves privacy while ensuring the reliable and secure completion of participant's operations.

This is a sample API that ICTFI provided for OneSource to handle the maximum number of characters for encryption (Figure 50). It includes functions for both encrypting and decrypting text, ensuring that data can be securely transmitted to character limits. The code is designed to work with various algorithms, allowing for flexibility depending on the application's security needs.


```
1 import requests
2
3 url = '[IP]:[Port]'
4 token = 'Add Token'
5
6 """
7 request_id: any number
8 algorithm: one of 'aes', 'rsa', and 'paillier'
9 ciphertext: any text, but for paillier it has to be a number
10 """
11 def encrypt(request_id, algorithm, text):
12     global url
13     complete_url = url + '/encrypt/'
14     if algorithm == 'paillier':
15         block_size = 0
16     else:
17         block_size = 100
18     text = str(text)
19     blocks = int(len(text) / block_size)
20     if blocks * block_size < len(text):
21         blocks += 1
22     cipher = ''
23     for i in range(blocks):
24         text_block = text[i*block_size:min((i+1)*block_size, len(text))]
25         jobject = {'id': str(request_id), 'text': text_block, 'algo': str(algorithm)}
26         cipher += ' '
27         try:
28             response = requests.post(complete_url, json=jobject, headers={'Authorization': f'Bearer {token}'})
29             cipher += str(response.json()['cipher'])
30         except:
31             try:
32                 cipher += str(response.json()['cipher'])
33             except:
34                 cipher += 'ERROR'
35                 break
36     cipher = cipher[1:]
37     return cipher
```

Figure 50 A sample of RESTful APIs to handle the maximum number of characters for encryption

```
39 """
40 request_id: any number that is previously used as request ID for encrypting the input ciphertext
41 algorithm: one of 'aes', 'rsa', and 'paillier'
42 ciphertext: any text that is previously encrypted by the same algorithm
43 """
44 def decrypt(request_id, algorithm, ciphertext):
45     global url
46     complete_url = url + '/decrypt/'
47     ciphertext = str(ciphertext)
48     blocks = ciphertext.split(' ')
49     plain = ''
50     for block in blocks:
51         jobject = {'id': str(request_id), 'cipher': block, 'algo': str(algorithm)}
52         plain += ' '
53         try:
54             response = requests.post(complete_url, json=jobject, headers={'Authorization': f'Bearer {token}'})
55             plain += str(response.json()['cleartext'])
56         except:
57             plain = 'integer'
58             break
59     plain = plain.replace(' ', '')
60     return plain
61
62 ##### how to use
63 request_id = 1
64 ciphertext = encrypt(request_id, 'aes', 'rigorous')
65 text = decrypt(request_id, 'aes', ciphertext)
66 print("In AES, '[text]' is encrypted into '(ciphertext)'.")
67
68 request_id = 2
69 ciphertext = encrypt(request_id, 'rsa', 'rigorous')
70 text = decrypt(request_id, 'rsa', ciphertext)
71 print("In RSA, '[text]' is encrypted into '(ciphertext)'.")
72
73 request_id = 3
74 ciphertext = encrypt(request_id, 'paillier', '1**300')
75 ciphertext = encrypt(request_id, 'paillier', '123')
76 text = decrypt(request_id, 'paillier', ciphertext)
77 print("In Paillier, '[text]' is encrypted into '(ciphertext)'.")
78
```

Figure 51 A sample of RESTful APIs to handle the summation with Paillier Encryption

Also, ICTFI has provided an updated API support secure summation for FL with Paillier Encryption (Figure 51). This API enables encryption, summation of encrypted values, and decryption, handling floating-point numbers directly without scaling. For example, the API successfully computes the decrypted sum of encrypted values 1.23 and 0.79875 as 2.02875 (Figure 52).

```
C:\Users\SONY\Desktop\AmirCT>kubectl get svc --kubeconfig=amir.kubeconfig --namespace=ictfi
NAME                TYPE          CLUSTER-IP      EXTERNAL-IP      PORT(S)          AGE
db                  LoadBalancer  10.43.200.38    10.1.1.13        5432:30111/TCP   41d
decryptor-aes       LoadBalancer  10.43.144.153   10.1.1.22        8023:32413/TCP   41d
decryptor-paillier  LoadBalancer  10.43.77.77     10.1.1.23        8033:32677/TCP   41d
decryptor-rsa       LoadBalancer  10.43.202.24    10.1.1.24        8003:31722/TCP   41d
encryptor-aes       LoadBalancer  10.43.243.222   10.1.1.18        8022:32704/TCP   41d
encryptor-paillier  LoadBalancer  10.43.75.114    10.1.1.19        8032:31995/TCP   41d
encryptor-rsa       LoadBalancer  10.43.138.37    10.1.1.21        8002:31755/TCP   41d
keygenerator        LoadBalancer  10.43.44.143    10.1.1.16        8005:31779/TCP   41d
keymanager          LoadBalancer  10.43.190.216   10.1.1.17        8001:31369/TCP   41d
requesthandler      LoadBalancer  10.43.215.122   10.1.1.15        8004:30333/TCP   41d
web                 LoadBalancer  10.43.165.38    10.1.1.14        80:30222/TCP     41d

C:\Users\SONY\Desktop>python API_EaaS.py
In AES, 'abcdefg' is encrypted into 'c0d0313d0bda29ad3ed9e4562c1b57e0'.

In RSA, 'abcdefg' is encrypted into '7ab00956f0e424999218e13857f1b305708bff196df9764cab0cbd389a4ef69e5e219bf65b98ea421c00013edaa084023b3ea49e4eff4e891af99d69ff416c99a1576022878c8c525eeab10ed453f2bb1734f49a9382ef64c0017ca9a39232b7f8347169'.

The decrypted of summation of 1.23 and 0.79875 in Paillier is 2.02875

C:\Users\SONY\Desktop>
```

Figure 52 The output of the summation API

7.3.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The EaaS framework integrates advanced data monitoring and service management features to ensure secure, efficient, and transparent operation of cryptographic processes across fog and cloud layers. Real-time monitoring tools are embedded within the Kubernetes infrastructure and service mesh, enabling continuous observation of resource utilization (CPU, memory), encryption/decryption latency, throughput rates, and component availability. This monitoring infrastructure lives into the dispatcher algorithm used by the Global Coordinator (GC), allowing intelligent task allocation based on current system load and node performance. Additionally, the system logs all service interactions, encryption requests, and API calls to maintain accountability, support traceability, and enable auditing. These logs include metadata such as timestamps, algorithm types used, participant IDs, and resource consumption metrics, which are securely stored and protected through encryption to prevent tampering or unauthorized access. Furthermore, the system supports service observability via dashboards and alerts that can identify anomalies, service delays, or node failures in real time. This capability enables dynamic scaling of resources and the seamless migration of services between fog and cloud layers. On the service side, EaaS provides customizable encryption and decryption operations via RESTful APIs, where users can specify the cryptographic algorithm, data scope, key management preferences, and processing duration. These features empower users with flexible and transparent access to secure services, while also enabling administrators to monitor operational KPIs, detect bottlenecks, and proactively manage security threats or resource shortages.

7.3.3. Final Results

The deployment and evaluation of the EaaS system within the ICT-FI testbed have demonstrated significant improvements in performance, scalability, and security. Through the adoption of the Full-Cloud-Fog architecture, the platform achieved an 81% increase in throughput, as reported in the real-world implementation. Dynamic resource allocation, enabled by the Kubernetes environment and optimized dispatching logic, allowed the system to handle fluctuating workloads while minimizing latency and reducing resource consumption. Notably, CPU and memory usage dropped by over 10% due to intelligent task scheduling and component placement strategies. Furthermore, the API tests confirmed the system's capability to handle both encrypted summation and character-level encryption for real-time FL scenarios using Paillier encryption, with minimal error and high computational efficiency. The secure interaction between EaaS and external modules, such as the PPFL detector, validated the framework's compatibility and effectiveness in multi-component secure ecosystems. Extensive security testing including attack simulations like man-in-the-middle, sniffing, and denial-of-service revealed the architecture's resilience, with no critical failures observed under stress conditions. The layered encryption scheme and the use of decentralized service replicas proved instrumental in mitigating insider and outsider threats.

7.3.4. Updates related to the first prototype

The first prototype of EaaS, developed by ICT-FI, was based on a basic public dataset and supported only limited message generation. In the updated version, the system has been significantly improved to support a real FL environment with multiple IIoT clients and a single aggregator server. It can now process structured encryption requests and generate complete and well-formatted messages based on real-world sandbox datasets, including DDoS attacks. The interaction between the anomaly detection module and EaaS has been refined, enabling encrypted model updates via EaaS during federated training. These updates improve both data privacy and system modularity, demonstrating the successful integration of secure encryption services into the FL workflow.

7.4. Privacy Preserving CTI Sharing - CTI

7.4.1. Component Architecture

The high-level component architecture of the privacy-preserving CTI sharing component is depicted in Figure 53. The asset is composed of an Identity Management component for access control of producers and consumers, a Policy Management Service for the administration of the privacy policies (received from the SO) that will be applied to the incoming event before its publication, a Secure Database so unmodified events can be stored for auditing purposes, the Anonymizer Service for the application of the supported Privacy Preserving and Data Mining techniques, and finally the TIP Proxy that acts as an intermediary for publication and synchronization of events.

Figure 53 Function architecture of Privacy-preserving CTI Sharing

The Anonymizer Service, which represents the core module of this asset, aims to protect the identified sensitive information of an event prior to its publication in the local MISP server. It implements several PETs that seek to minimize the risks associated with re-identification, such as attribute disclosure and identity disclosure. Below, the list of supported techniques is detailed:

1. Suppression
2. Generalization
3. K-anonymity
4. K-map
5. L-diversity
6. Differential Privacy

The usage of a specific technique can be specified initially by the data owner in the privacy policies. These privacy policies consist of two main files:

- Privacy policy file defines the techniques (PETs) to be applied on a set of attributes of the event that is to be published.
- Hierarchy policy file defines the level of transformations to be applied over the data for each PET specified in the previous privacy policy file.

The K-Anonymity and K-map techniques used are explained below.

K-Anonymity: This is the condition of a dataset that ensures that each record is indistinguishable from at least k-1 other records with respect to quasi-identifiers (attributes that can indirectly identify individuals). This is achieved by grouping records into equivalence classes and generalizing or suppressing the values of the quasi-identifiers so that each group contains at least k records. Therefore, K-Anonymity uses transformation techniques such as suppression and generalization to satisfy its condition. This technique in our service is applicable to events that present multiple instances of the same object type. Just as we describe it theoretically by referring to tables and records, in the practice of our use case, objects of the same event type will be grouped, and the

attributes considered 'quasi' will be transformed, using suppression/generalization as transformation techniques. Once the 'quasi' attributes have been transformed for each hierarchy or privacy level indicated in the policy, they are grouped into equivalence classes using the ARX library to perform the necessary calculations and check whether the 'K' indicated for this type of object is satisfied.

K-Map: This is an extension of the k-anonymity technique that improves privacy by considering not only the dataset in question but also an external reference dataset. This technique ensures that each record in the anonymized dataset is indistinguishable from at least k individuals in the general population represented by the reference dataset. In our case, previously, with the k-anonymity technique, we only considered objects from a single event, that is, from a single instant in time. However, using this technique, we batch all events published through this PrivServ service instance, grouping all quasi-objects of the same type and applying k-anonymity in the same way as before. It should also be noted that our service stores the events published through it in their original form prior to transformation.

7.4.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

This assets receives logs data from an IDS whose private data is wanted to be anonymized prior to being shared as CTI information. In particular it receives log row data from Snort , that is used in RIGOUROUS use cases.

Example of Data log obtained from SNORT to be anonymized before being shared is shown in Table 23:

Table 23 Data log obtained from SNORT

Field	Description
Data log	"77353b12-3642-463c-983b-724355cccb85", "Object": [{ "name": "snortlog", "uuid": "c9cf6e8b-39c5-4784-ba3a-3d5a2cc705f8", "Attribute": [{ "uuid": "2f6574d6-e2e8-49ba-805d-20c2aa7e6dd7", "object_relation": "Alert", "value": "[**] [1:4000004:1] DDoS attack detected [**]", }, { "uuid": "8bea7587-a980-4911-b6ed-b80e87128584", "object_relation": "Message", "value": "TCP TTL:58 TOS:0x0 ID:67408 IpLen:20 DgmLen:60 ***S***** Seq: 0x0 Ack: 0x0 Win: 0x200 TcpLen: 20", }, { "uuid": "7d083cb1-39a2-4a60-98e3-6c35e9faae77", "object_relation": "Date",

	<pre> "value": "09/12", }, { "uuid": "f72b2d19-a53a-436e-8397-83cfb5005f3a", "object_relation": "Time", "value": "18:16:19.958", }, { "uuid": "366bf9ea-4cbd-4fa7-b2c5-8dc2b02e0fdc", "object_relation": "IP_Dst", "value": "133.44.8.163", }, { "uuid": "5d60a631-d7b2-4f9d-a983-7100c358cab2", "object_relation": "Port_Dst", "value": "1992", },], "distribution": "5", "sharing_group_id": "0", "meta-category": "network", "template_uuid": "daa750b8-9ec3-49ff-8bae-14e96fb7cbf0", "description": "snortlog data object" }, </pre>
--	---

7.4.3. Final Results

To demonstrate the feasibility of the proposal, we have tested a use case where Snort logs files are first obfuscated and then shared as CTI data through MISP tool. The anonymizer receives as input a k-map policy that is then used for obfuscating the IP addresses that are present in the IDS Snort files.

To demonstrate the application of K-Map to an object or data, records of that data type must previously exist in the context of the PrivServ service, as we want to verify that the technique uses that context to meet the condition established in the policy.

For this case, these six SNORT logs objects have previously been introduced into the service context through an anonymization request. Therefore, after anonymization and publication, they are recorded in the service database, which can later retrieve them when requesting to apply the K-Map technique to objects of that type, as we will see in this example in Figure 54.

```
repos > demo_datasets > dataset_test6_objs.csv > data
1
2 0 ID:67408 IpLen:20 DgmLen:60 ***S***** Seq: 0x0 Ack: 0x0 Win: 0x200 TcpLen: 20,09/12,18:16:19.958,133.44.8.163,1992,192.168.10.3,5479
3 :20825 IpLen:20 DgmLen:48 ***PA**** Seq: 0x61958110 Ack: 0x34717296 Win: 0x100 TcpLen: 20,09/12,18:16:25.958,138.20.136.51,16706,192.168.32.5,3031
4 0 ID:67408 IpLen:20 DgmLen:60 ***S***** Seq: 0x0 Ack: 0x0 Win: 0x200 TcpLen: 20,09/12,18:16:19.958,133.44.8.163,1992,192.168.11.2,28809
5 :20825 IpLen:20 DgmLen:48 ***PA**** Seq: 0x61958110 Ack: 0x34717296 Win: 0x100 TcpLen: 20,09/12,18:16:25.958,138.20.136.51,16706,10.20.1.35,2444
6 0 ID:67408 IpLen:20 DgmLen:60 ***S***** Seq: 0x0 Ack: 0x0 Win: 0x200 TcpLen: 20,09/12,18:16:19.958,133.44.8.163,1992,10.20.1.125,30011
7 :20825 IpLen:20 DgmLen:48 ***PA**** Seq: 0x61958110 Ack: 0x34717296 Win: 0x100 TcpLen: 20,09/12,18:16:25.958,138.20.136.51,16706,192.168.12.102,5081
```

Figure 54 K-Map example

Now, we want to apply 2-Map to an event containing this type of ids-log object. In the following Figure 55, you can see the data for two new objects that we will publish in the new MISP event.

```
repos > demo_datasets > dataset_test2_objs.csv > data
1 st
2 0x0 ID:67408 IpLen:20 DgmLen:60 ***S***** Seq: 0x0 Ack: 0x0 Win: 0x200 TcpLen: 20,09/12,18:16:19.958,133.44.8.163,1992,192.168.32.121,30011
3 ID:20825 IpLen:20 DgmLen:48 ***PA**** Seq: 0x61958110 Ack: 0x34717296 Win: 0x100 TcpLen: 20,09/12,18:16:25.958,138.20.136.51,16706,192.168.35.1,5081
```

Figure 55 2-Map example

To apply 2-Map, first create the policy in the GUI by selecting the object type you want to privatize, the specific attribute you want to hide, specifying the $k = 2$ parameter, and selecting the k-map application checkbox.

Then, create the hierarchy file that will indicate how to hide the attribute in ascending order of hiding level, using regular expressions (Figure 56).

Figure 56 Privacy policy from dashboard

Anonymized SNORT event published in MISP after obfuscation by the pp-CTI tool using the k-map (Figure 57):

Date	Time	IP_Src	Port_Src	IP_Dst	Port_Dst	Organization	Object name	References
2024-09-15	09:12	133.44.8.163	1992	192.168.*	30011	Organisation	Object name: ds-log	
2024-09-15	18:16:19.956					Organisation	Alert: comment	[*] [1:3000003:1] Malware detected [*]
2024-09-15						Organisation	Priority: comment	1
2024-09-15						Organisation	Message: comment	TCP TTL:62 TOS:0x0 ID:20825 (sLem:20 DgnLen:49 ***9***** Seq: 0x61898110 Ack: 0x34717296 Win: 0x100 TcptLen: 20
2024-09-15	09:12					Organisation	Date: comment	09:12
2024-09-15	18:16:25.956					Organisation	Time: comment	18:16:25.956
2024-09-15		138.20.136.51				Organisation	IP_Src: comment	
2024-09-15			16706			Organisation	Port_Src: comment	
2024-09-15				192.168.*		Organisation	IP_Dst: comment	
2024-09-15					5061	Organisation	Port_Dst: comment	

Figure 57 Anonymized SNORT event published in MISP after obfuscation by the pp-CTI tool using the k-map

As it can be seen, our anonymizer tool has successfully obfuscated sensible attribute as IP addresses.

7.4.4. Updates related to the first prototype

In this final version, the pp-CTI component has been extended to support additional privacy-preserving techniques. In particular, K-anonymity and k-map have been fully implemented in the anonymizer service. To demonstrate the feasibility of the proposal, we have tested a use case where Snort logs files are obfuscated and then shared as CTI data through MISP.

8 COMPONENT INTEROPERABILITY

To ensure robust and coordinated security workflows in complex cyber-physical environments, WP4 integrates a suite of AI-powered components that operate as interconnected yet modular assets. These components are designed to work collaboratively across network layers, system domains, and data silos. Ensuring their interoperability is key to achieving fast, intelligent, and privacy-compliant responses to evolving threats.

This last main section of the deliverable describes how the WP4 assets, developed across different partners and aligned to specific functionalities, interconnect and exchange information within the RIGOUROUS architecture. The subsections that follow provide a high-level architectural overview of these components and detail the interaction flows that govern their collaboration, enforcement cycles, and dynamic adaptation mechanisms.

8.1. Architectural overview and composition strategy

The WP4 architecture of the RIGOUROUS project is designed as a modular, scalable, and loosely coupled ecosystem that enables AI-based detection, contextual decision-making, privacy-preserving analysis, and automated mitigation in cyber-physical infrastructures. Each WP4 component contributes as a building block in a layered security pipeline and is developed to interoperate through standardized interfaces, messaging protocols, and data formats.

There are several tightly interconnected building blocks, each playing a distinct role in the security loop.

- 6G infrastructure layer and data plane provide continuous telemetry to the Monitoring & Analytics block. It captures data from IoT devices/controllers, gateways and network layer and feeds the SAE module for AI-driven anomaly detection. This feedback ensures that analytical decisions are always contextualized with the latest infrastructure status.
- The SAE includes the Privacy preserving federated AI anomaly detection which uses privacy-preserving mechanisms to detect distributed threats, the MTD-based Robust AI, which enhances model adaptability and unpredictability under adversarial conditions, and the CPC which is responsible for correlating anomalies across network layers and physical systems, using traffic and behaviour profiling. Together, these components form the analytical brain of the WP4 architecture, fusing detection with risk awareness and robustness.
- Cognitive decision, orchestration and security management is composed of the AI-Driven Decision Engine, ZTM and TRA (led by EBOS), this block consumes alerts from the Security Analytics Engines, performs severity assessment, and recommends tailored mitigation plans based on dynamic threat scoring and system-criticality mapping.
- The SOAR translates AID recommendations into enforcement actions. Also, the SOAR topology monitors continuously monitor and update the global state, ensuring that decisions made by AID consider the most recent infrastructure layout.
- The core of the Reaction plane is the security response and mitigation which automatically adapts and repairs configurations when enforcement fails or when interoperability mismatches are detected (e.g., gateway/RES protocol incompatibilities).

8.2. Component collaboration flow

All the building blocks interact in a coordinated loop that supports intelligent and autonomous threat mitigation.

- Detection phase (SAE): The CPC and the other modules of the SAE block, leverage AI classifiers, detect anomalies such as abnormal control patterns, malicious actions, unauthorised injections, etc. These are fed by telemetry collected from the 6G infrastructure layer and formatted by the Monitoring and Analytics module. Federated models execute locally across distributed nodes, preserving privacy while sharing model updates securely.
- Analysis phase (Cognitive Management): The AID generates a contextual mitigation plan—this may include blocking sources, altering control paths, or pausing operations. The TRA assesses the severity and relevance of the detected threat, scoring the risk based on component criticality and historical behaviour.
- Mitigation phase (Response and enforcement): The Security Orchestrator pushes control actions to the relevant Security Agents, either via variable updates or enforcement policies (e.g., DROP rules). If these fail, the Digital Twin validates the current state and triggers DASC, which resolves interoperability mismatches by dynamically adapting service parameters or control bindings.
- Feedback and adaptation phase: The SOAR monitor continually feeds updated topology data and mitigation effectiveness into the TRA and CPC modules. MTD is applied to the learning pipeline, altering attack surfaces and defending against adapting adversaries.

This orchestrated collaboration enables real-time, privacy-preserving, and context-aware cyber threat detection and remediation across RIGOUROUS use cases.

9 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has presented the final results of the assets developed within WP4, detailing the maturity, functionality, and final status of each component as of project M30. Building on the previous progress reported in D4.2 [2], the current document consolidates the architecture, technical updates, and validation results for each WP4 module.

The AI-Driven Anomaly Detection section elaborated on novel privacy-preserving, federated deep learning techniques applied to the identification of anomalous behaviours in B5G and 6G network environments, using models such as Autoencoders and Multi-Layer Perceptrons. The Cognitive Decision-Making module has been enhanced to translate anomaly alerts into impact assessments and mitigation strategies, integrated with risk scoring from the Threat Risk Assessor. The Security Response-Mitigation section demonstrated automated mitigation workflows using tools like the AI-driven EDoS Mitigator and the DASC component, which addressed IoT and protocol mismatch vulnerabilities. Network Flow and Topology Monitoring tools completed the SOAR sensing loop, providing targeted insights across virtual domains. Meanwhile, privacy-preserving AI technologies such as MTD, EaaS, and CTI-sharing modules further enhanced the resilience and trustworthiness of the security intelligence chain.

This deliverable also highlights how these components interoperate through well-defined interfaces, supporting end-to-end orchestration and automation. Several assets have been deployed and validated across the use cases in the pilot testbeds. These implementations serve as preparatory steps for full integration in WP5, where the complete WP4 stack will be evaluated across RIGOUROUS use cases. The insights from D4.3 mark a key milestone in delivering advanced, AI-driven cybersecurity solutions tailored to future networked infrastructures.

10 REFERENCES

- [1] RIGOUROUS, "D4.1 Design Plan of the AI-driven Anomaly Detection, Decision and Mitigation," <https://umu-projects.inf.um.es/products/files/doceditor.aspx?fileid=10585&action=view>.
- [2] RIGOUROUS, "D4.2 First Results of the AI-Driven Anomaly Detection, Decision and Mitigation," <https://umu-projects.inf.um.es/products/files/doceditor.aspx?fileid=12025>.
- [3] S. K. Poorazad, C. Benzaïd, and T. Taleb, "A novel buffered federated learning framework for privacy-driven anomaly detection in IIoT," in Proc. of IEEE Globecom'24, Cape Town, South Africa, Dec. 2024.
- [4] Online: Available at: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/wardac/applicationlayer-ddos-dataset>.
- [5] RIGOUROUS, "D5.2 Platform Prototype Integration and In-lab testing 2," <https://umu-projects.inf.um.es/products/files/doceditor.aspx?fileid=13126>
- [6] Online: Available at: <https://github.com/jseidl/GoldenEye.git>
- [7] Online: Available at <https://github.com/hellgrenj/hulken.git>
- [8] Online: Available at <https://github.com/gkbrk/slowloris.git>
- [9] S. K. Poorazad, C. Benzaïd, and T. Taleb, "A novel buffered federated learning framework for privacy-driven anomaly detection in IIoT," in Proc. of IEEE Globecom'24, Cape Town, South Africa, Dec. 2024.
- [10] C. Benzaïd, T. Taleb, A. Sami, and O. Hireche. FortisEDoS: A Deep Transfer Learning-empowered Economical Denial of Sustainability Detection Framework for Cloud-Native Network Slicing. IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing, 21(4): 2818-2835, July-Aug. 2024, doi: 10.1109/TDSC.2023.3318606.
- [11] C. Benzaïd, T. Taleb, A. Sami, and O. Hireche. A Deep Transfer Learning-powered EDoS Detection Mechanism for 5G and Beyond Network Slicing. In Proc. of IEEE Globecom'23, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Dec. 2023
- [12] "Dynamic Admission Control," Kubernetes Documentation, [online]. Available: <https://kubernetes.io/docs/reference/access-authn-authz/extensible-admission-controllers/>. Accessed on 05 June 2025
- [13] "kube-apiserver Admission (v1)," Kubernetes Documentation, [online]. Available: <https://kubernetes.io/docs/reference/config-api/apiserver-admission.v1/>. Accessed on 05 June 2025
- [14] "Open5GS," [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Gradiant/5g-charts>. Accessed on 05 June 2025
- [15] "UERAN-SIM," [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/aligungr/UERANSIM>. Accessed on 05 June 2025
- [16] V. Mnih et al., "Human-level control through deep reinforcement learning," J.Nature, vol. 518, no. 7540, pp. 529 533, 2015
- [17] Y. Lu et al., "Low-latency federated learning and blockchain for edge association in digital twin empowered 6g networks," IEEE Trans. on Industrial Informatics, vol. 17, no. 7, pp. 5098 5107, 2020

- [18] S. Kianpisheh and T. Taleb, "Collaborative federated learning for 6g with a deep reinforcement learning based controlling mechanism: A ddos attack detection scenario," *IEEE Trans. on Network and Service Management*, DoI: 10.1109/TNSM.2024.3387987, 2024
- [19] Sharafaldin et al., "Developing realistic distributed denial of service attack dataset and taxonomy," in *Conf. on Security Technology*, 2019
- [20] I. Sharafaldin et al., "Toward generating a new intrusion detection dataset and intrusion traffic characterization," *Conf. on Information Systems Security and Privacy*, 2018
- [21] I. Sharafaldin, A. H. Lashkari, A. A. Ghorbani et al., "Toward generating a new intrusion detection dataset and intrusion traffic characterization." *ICISSp*, vol. 1, no. 2018, pp. 108-116, 2018
- [22] R. Al Mallah et al., "Untargeted poisoning attack detection in federated learning via behavior attestation," *IEEE Access*, 2023
- [23] "NFStream," [Online]. Available: <https://www.nfstream.org/>.
- [24] I. Sharafaldin, A. H. Lashkari and A. A. Ghorbani, "Toward Generating a New Intrusion Detection Dataset and Intrusion Traffic Characterization," in *4th International Conference on Information Systems Security and Privacy (ICISSP), Portugal, January 2018*.
- [25] J. Henriques, A. Gomes and L. Cordeiro, "IoT for Improving First Responders' Situational Awareness and Safety on Federated 5G Testbeds," Jun. 2022
- [26] "mqtt-stresser," [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/inovex/mqtt-stresser>.
- [27] "curl," [Online]. Available: <https://curl.se/>.
- [28] National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), "National Vulnerability Database (NVD)," [Online]. Available: <https://nvd.nist.gov/general>.
- [29] MITRE, "Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE)," [Online]. Available: <https://www.cve.org/>.
- [30] Javadpour, A., Ja'fari, F., Taleb, T., Zhao, Y., Yang, B., & Benzaïd, C. (2023). Encryption as a service for IoT: Opportunities, challenges, and solutions. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 11(5), 7525-7558.
- [31] Javadpour, A., Ja'fari, F., & Taleb, T. (2024, June). Encryption as a service: A review of architectures and taxonomies. In *IFIP International Conference on Distributed Applications and Interoperable Systems* (pp. 36-44). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland
- [32] Javadpour, A., Ja'fari, F., Taleb, T., Benzaïd, C., Bin, Y., & Zhao, Y. (2024). Encryption as a service (EaaS): Introducing the full-cloud-fog architecture for enhanced performance and security. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*
- [33] Javadpour, A., Ja'fari, F., Taleb, T., Benzaïd, C., Rosa, L., Tomás, P., & Cordeiro, L. (2024, September). Deploying testbed docker-based application for encryption as a service in Kubernetes. In *2024 International Conference on Software, Telecommunications and Computer Networks (SoftCOM)* (pp. 1-7). IEEE
- [34] Tomas, P.R., Felix, P., Rosa, L., Gomes, A.S., Cordeiro, L. (2024). A Novel Approach for Continual and Federated Network Anomaly Detection. In: Arai, K. (eds) *Proceedings of the Future Technologies Conference (FTC) 2024, Volume 4*. FTC 2024. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 1157. Springer, Cham
- [35] Pedro Tomás, Samira Kamali Poorazad, Chafika Benzaïd, Luis Rosa, Jorge Proença, Tarik Taleb, and Luis Cordeiro. Enhancing Federated Learning with Homomorphic Encryption and Multi-Party Computation for Improved Privacy. In *proceedings of the 2024 IEEE Future Networks*
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Dissemination level: PU

World Forum (FNWF), Dubai, United Arab Emirates, 2024, pp. 891-896

- [36] Pedro R. Tomas, Sofia Silva, Marco Neto, Jorge Proença, Luis Rosa, Luis Cordeiro, Tarik Taleb, Tiago Cruz. Network Policy Enforcement in cloud-native environments. In: proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI 2025), Cyprus University of Technology, Limassol, Cyprus, 26-29 Jun. 2025
- [37] Online: Available at: <https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/ids-2018.html>